

**CARIBBEAN
BIOLOGICAL
CORRIDOR**

Strategic Plan for the Caribbean Biological Corridor 2022-2030

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December 2022

Document prepared by the Caribbean Biological Corridor Secretariat within the framework of the project “Strengthening the Caribbean Biological Corridor”, developed with the generous contribution of the European Union and the support of the United Nations Environment Program. This version was approved in Decision number 13, of the CBC’s Ministerial Committee held on December 6, 2022 in Santo Domingo, Dominican Republic.

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1

Introduction

THE CARIBBEAN BIOLOGICAL CORRIDOR INITIATIVE has developed a strengthening process in which its general foundations and conceptual model have been scientifically redefined and consolidated, new conservation priorities have been agreed upon, a new and much broader spatial demarcation has been established, the foundations for its future development have been laid, and the mechanisms for its institutionality and financial sustainability have been defined and put into operation. An essential and culminating tool to undertake the new stage of development of the initiative is its Strategic Plan 2022-2030.

The plan, in addition to responding to the priorities agreed for the initiative, aims to serve as a tool to complement and support the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development in the countries of the initiative. To this end, it considers and is aligned with the UNEP Medium-Term Strategy for 2022-2025 - en route to 2030, and with the Post-2020 Global Framework for Biological Diversity, to be approved at COP 15 on Biodiversity. Recognizing the role of the European Union in supporting the initiative, the Plan has taken into account the Biodiversity Strategy for Latin America and the Caribbean of the European Union (Beyond the Jaguar); as well as has considered the Strategy of the Caribbean Community (CARICOM) for the implementation of the Global Strategic Plan for Biological Diversity of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) until 2022 and beyond. It is intended to ensure that the work of the CBC, far from representing an additional burden, helps the initiative's member countries to respond to their commitments with the Multilateral Environmental Agreements to which they are a party. Amongst them the Plan should contribute to the Agreements of the Forum of Ministers of Latin America and the Caribbean, the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework and the commitments emanating from the Glasgow Climate Summit, while taking as a reference the cooperation frameworks for development that the United Nations has signed with the countries.

The document is divided into six main sections, in addition to the introduction. Section 2 summarizes the geographical context, the history of the development of the CBC initiative, its governance model and operating structure, and the progress made in its implementation. Section 3 explains the identified conservation priorities. Section 4 describes the design of the initiative, in terms of its conceptual axes, objectives, mission and vision, conceptual model, spatial demarcation and expected benefits of the initiative. Section 5 presents the analysis of the current situation, both from the point of view of conservation, institutional and financial spheres. Finally, Section 6 presents the strategic program, which starts from the Theory of Change to present the strategic goals of intervention, the expected outcomes, outputs, and activities that must be implemented to achieve the established goals. Subsequently, a schedule of activities organized by work programs is presented and, finally a general estimated budget is presented. The plan's document is complemented with several annexes, including a Logical Framework that details the indicators to measure the progress of the plan by outcomes and outputs. ●

A photograph of a mangrove forest with blue water and a blue sky with light clouds. The text is overlaid on the image.

2

Context and Initial Situation

2.1 GEOGRAPHIC CONTEXT

The insular Caribbean is one of the “biodiversity hotspots” identified as a global priority for conservation. It comprises more than 7,000 islands of various sizes, from the largest, Cuba, with more than 100,000 km², to territories of less than 300 km² and numerous even smaller islets and keys. It is in the migratory route of numerous marine and bird species, as well as that of many of the Atlantic’s tropical cyclones. In just 0.15% of the planet’s surface, the Antilles have one of the highest relative richness and endemism rates in the world, with more than 12,500 species of vertebrates and vascular plants, of which 70% are only found in the Caribbean. The Caribbean Sea, comprising only 0.8% of the global ocean, has an endemism rate of 26% in the species belonging to the best-known marine taxa. Connectivity, in turn, is manifested in the migratory cycles of millions of individuals of birds, fish, turtles and marine mammals, and in the dispersion and exchange of seeds and larvae of fish, corals, crustaceans and mollusks throughout the region, under the impulse of the complex systems of marine currents and winds. All these factors make carrying out coordinated actions between the states of the region an essential although very complex task if conservation goals and sustainable use of biodiversity resources are to be attained.

The Greater Antilles are essentially made up by the islands that conform the territories of Cuba, Haiti, Jamaica, Puerto Rico, and the Dominican Republic. With their 207,411 km² these islands cover almost 90% of the land mass of the entire insular Caribbean and are home to more than 90% of its population and its wealth of biodiversity. If the extension of its Exclusive Economic Zones is added, this insular group covers an area of about 1,480,000 km², equivalent to approximately 23% of the marine and insular territory of the Greater Caribbean. The present stage of the Caribbean Biological Corridor initiative is being developed in this area.

2.2 EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE CBC INITIATIVE

At the crossroads of the global crises of accelerating biodiversity loss, climate change, and increased pollution, the environmental authorities of Cuba, the Dominican Republic, and Haiti took a visionary step in July 2007, when they joined forces and created the Biological Corridor in the Caribbean (CBC). Since then, the CBC has become a multinational initiative that works in a coordinated manner to produce transformative changes aimed at reducing direct threats to biodiversity, mitigating and adapting to climate change, and promoting sustainable and equitable development models in the region.

The CBC has proven to be a successful mechanism in maintaining bilateral negotiations and cross-border articulation around environmental issues. It is also recognized as a strong platform for South-South cooperation on environmental issues. The CBC contributes to the implementation of international agendas and initiatives such as:

- The objectives of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.
- The Post-2020 Global Framework for Biodiversity.
- The Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Objectives within the framework of the Glasgow Declaration and Agreements, emanating from COP 26 on Climate Change.
- The United Nations Decade for Ecosystem Restoration
- The United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development
- The Cartagena Convention for the Protection and Development of the Marine Environment of the Wider Caribbean Region, of which CBC member countries are also members.

▲ Signing of the declaration of Santo Domingo.

When it was founded in 2007, the CBC was limited to the eastern region of Cuba and the western part of Hispaniola. Its fundamental objective has been to facilitate a relationship between human beings and nature in a delimited geographical space, in such a way that connectivity between landscapes, habitats and cultures is ensured; biological diversity, ecological processes and environmental services are maintained; and a sustainable development model is promoted (Declaration of Santo Domingo 2007).

The CBC has directly implemented three projects that, with the financial contribution of the European Union and the support of UNEP, have allowed the initiative to advance. The project for the Delimitation and establishment of the Caribbean Biological Corridor (2011-2014) with a contribution from the European Union of more than two million euros, made it possible to begin the implementation of the initiative and established the bases for its subsequent development. It was focused on the first spatial demarcation of the initiative, the strengthening of terrestrial protected areas, capacity building, the facilitation of exchanges, the rehabilitation of degraded areas, the improvement of the livelihood of local communities and the establishment of a governance structure. and trinational coordination.

An important result was the launch in 2009 of an Action Plan that proposed 59 actions grouped into 8 thematic lines. This Plan served as the basis for subsequent work and the development of projects and, although fragmented, it was possible to implement its fundamental aspects.

▲ Biodiversity monitoring in the Greater Antilles

In this first stage, the governance structure of the corridor was also formalized; At the same time research, monitoring, capacity building and rural development projects were carried out on the ground. The governance mechanism of the CBC has been functioning since its creation and has held regular coordination meetings at the ministerial level and has facilitated the signing of Cooperation Agreements and the execution of concerted actions.

An important milestone was the 2014 Inter-ministerial Agreement on Guidelines for the future development of the CBC, which identified several priority areas for future work:

1. The continued strengthening of the CBC initiative.
2. The consolidation and expansion of cooperation and exchange actions in protected areas.
3. The rehabilitation of degraded areas and the identification and application of livelihood alternatives for the communities.
4. Capacity building.
5. Outreach, communication, and education.
6. The maintenance and expansion of the coordinating structure of the CBC initiative.

Specific guidelines were established for each of these areas. Among those that had the most impact for the conception of the present stage with the CBC Strengthening project, are:

1. Strengthening of the CBC initiative:

- a. Carry out the delimitation of the CBC marine space considering the climate change that affects the CBC area,
- b. Promote the inclusion of the regional approach to biodiversity conservation in national strategies

2.2. Consolidation and expansion of cooperation and exchange actions in protected areas:

- a. Jointly evaluate conservation objects with regional and/or continental importance, plan management and/or monitoring actions in an integrated manner, and reconcile the methodologies applied in planning and management.
- b. Development of a binational mechanism for the management of the transboundary Biosphere Reserve between the Dominican Republic and Haiti

3. Rehabilitation of degraded areas and identification and application of livelihood alternatives for communities:

- a. Establish synergies for a reforestation campaign
- b. Multiply the use of alternative energy sources with an emphasis on localities and cities where there is a greater demand for energy due to the use of firewood and coal.

4. Capacity building:

- a. Promote the exchanges of managers and decision makers of the countries and start them with the participation of the private sectors.
- b. Initiate training actions in the service and productive sectors.
- c. Promote alliances with universities for the training of professionals in areas of interest to the Corridor, as well as promote the extension activities of these universities to contribute to the objectives of the CBC
- d. Follow up on the results of the Haiti-Cuba exchange.

5. Awareness, communication, and education:

- a. Continue the dissemination of the CBC's objectives and results in various formats and languages.
- b. Increase the availability of information about the CBC for mass media.
- c. Maintain the operation and updating of the website.

6. Maintenance and expansion of the coordinating structure of the CBC initiative:

- a. Maintenance of the CBC coordinator structure with human and financial resources
- b. Expansion of the CBC with the inclusion of new countries.
- c. Give the mandate to the CBC Secretariat to:
 - i. Work together with the representatives of the three countries to ensure financial sustainability
 - ii. Update the initiative's long-term strategy
 - iii. Establish synergies to support and strengthen control over synergistic multinational projects.

As a result of its work during its first 10 years, the CBC became a permanent environmental coordination mechanism among member countries and an agent of understanding in the search for solutions to common problems. Among its main achievements are:

- Systematically maintain a regional coordination meeting mechanism at the ministerial level of the CBC countries, which has facilitated the achievement of formal agreements and the development of coordinated actions.
- The development of 10 projects in communities of the three countries with more than

2,000 favored communities, plus several projects developed by other institutions that contribute to the objectives of the CBC.

- Promotion of the use of alternative energy sources that reduce or eliminate the use of firewood and charcoal with more than 5,000 people benefited.
- More than 80 training actions carried out with more than 3,000 participants, on topics such as: components of Caribbean biodiversity, threats, sustainable development, adaptation to climate change, taxonomy, and integrated marine coastal management.
- Carrying out multiple communication actions, developing materials such as documentaries, media interventions, exhibitions, brochures, and other graphic materials.
- Studies of the migratory routes of various species and the impact of hurricanes on biodiversity.
- Studies and monitoring of conservation objects of regional importance.
- A regionally important biodiversity monitoring system under development.
- An Integrated Knowledge Management System in development, with more than 4,000 records and 1,350 geo-referenced layers of 18 topics related to the CBC.

2.3 CURRENT LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The CBC emerged in 2007 as an environmental political will endorsed by the ministers in charge of the Environment in Cuba, Haiti, and the Dominican Republic, in the Declaration of Santo Domingo, which was signed with the accompaniment of UNEP as the initiative's support agency.

Later, in 2009, with the signing of a new document calling itself the II Declaration of Santo Domingo, the will to implement the CBC initiative defined in 2007 was ratified, for which the ministers of the countries involved committed to the initiative stated the “willingness to allocate human, economic and in-kind resources, to the extent possible”, and indicate the development of a participatory action plan that includes, among others, concrete actions to:

- The design and execution of a joint research program on Caribbean biodiversity.
- The formulation and implementation of strategic actions for the development of the potential of protected areas, especially linked to sustainable tourism
- Identify and execute actions with nations from other areas of the continent, and from other areas of the planet that are part of the migratory routes of shared species in order to guarantee the protection of their habitat.
- Execute a reforestation plan as green infrastructure for adaptation and reduction of vulnerability to the effects of climate change.

In 2014, the Inter-ministerial Agreement of the Biological Corridor in the Caribbean was signed. This document, although not binding, goes beyond a declaration of political will, and not only reaffirms the commitment to the initiative, but also for the first time agrees on a document with a legal format that defines and supports several core aspects of the CBC, including:

- The institutional structure for the governance of the initiative.
- The functions of the different organs that comprise said structure.
- The mechanism for the incorporation of new countries to the initiative.
- The mechanism for revising the demarcation of the CBC.

► Caribbean mangrove ecosystem, nursery for fish and invertebrates.

In fact, the 2014 Inter-ministerial Agreement became the legal reference for the existence and development of the CBC.

2.4 GOVERNANCE MODEL AND OPERATING STRUCTURE

The foundations of the governance model and operating structure of the CBC were established by the Caribbean Biological Corridor Inter-Ministerial Agreement of November 13, 2014. The initiative's governance model and structure (Figure 1) is the guarantee for channeling conservation actions at all intervention scales of the initiative. To achieve its effective operation, the CBC governance system establishes the periodic review of the agreements reached by the countries, evaluates the progress of its strategic plan, and establishes regional priorities that are incorporated into the work agenda of the countries and of the Secretariat of the CBC. It is made up of four essential structures: The Ministerial Committee, the Scientific-Technical Committee, the Secretariat, and the Focal Points. The functions approved for each of these bodies are presented below, according to Decisions number 18 and 19 of the Ministerial Committee of November 2019, held in Havana, Cuba.

2.4.1 Ministerial Committee

The Ministerial Committee is the supreme decision-making body of the CBC initiative and is made up of the ministers in charge of environmental affairs in the countries that have joined the initiative. UNEP, through its Regional Office for Latin America and the Caribbean, is a permanent guest as Observer of the initiative that, in addition, provides technical, operational, administrative, and human resources assistance to the initiative and, in particular, for the operation of its Secretariat. Additionally, they may be invited as Observers of the Ministerial Committee, the ministers of the environment of other countries, plus one (1) representative of the non-governmental organizations of each Signatory Country and one (1) representative of the private sector of each of the Signatory Countries, elected according to the internal election mechanisms of those groups.

The Ministerial Committee establishes the policies that will be applied within the framework of the CBC, including the execution of projects. More specifically, the Ministerial Committee has established the following functions:

1. Facilitate the harmonization of policies at various levels (community, district, national and regional) in relation to the CBC implementation process.
2. Provide policy guidance regarding the implementation of the CBC.
3. Approve the work plans and strategic programs of the CBC that will be implemented by the Secretariat.
4. Approve the scientific-technical recommendations formulated by the Scientific-Technical Committee.
5. Approve the budgets of the initiative.

2.4.2 Scientific-Technical Committee

To ensure an informed decision-making process, the Ministerial Committee relies on its Technical Committee. As its name indicates, this committee reviews the documents submitted to it by the CBC Secretariat and provides the necessary technical inputs and advice to the Ministerial Committee for decision-making. The CBC Scientific-Technical Committee has defined the following functions:

1. Review the technical relevance of the specific interventions that will be taken as part of the projects developed by the Secretariat and advise the corresponding entities, as appropriate.
2. Advise the Ministerial Committee on the technical aspects of the implementation of projects for the benefit of the Caribbean Biological Corridor.
3. Provide technical strategic guidance on the future evolution of the Caribbean Biological Corridor.
4. Facilitate intersectoral technical discussions and actions on the different aspects of the Caribbean Biological Corridor.
5. Provide the Secretariat with inputs for the preparation of the annual work plan.
6. Provide contributions and technical guidance on the technical aspects of the implementation of the Caribbean Biological Corridor, including the definition of the demarcation area of the Caribbean Biological Corridor and the technical justification for carrying it out.
7. Follow up in each signatory country of the agreements adopted by the Ministerial Committee.
8. Review the technical, administrative, and financial reports of the Secretariat and formulate technical recommendations for the consideration and approval of the Ministerial Committee.

2.4.3 Secretariat

The CBC Secretariat is the coordinating and implementing arm of the initiative, with both a scientific-technical and an executive role. This mechanism has been operating for more than 10 years and constitutes an effective tool to implement coordinated actions. Its approved functions are listed below:

1. Implement the decisions of the Ministerial Committee and the Technical Committee.
2. Account for their management to the Technical Committee and the Ministerial Committee.
3. Mobilize and manage funds for the implementation of the Caribbean Biological Corridor Initiative, its work plans, and projects.
4. Prepare the drafts of the work plan and annual budget of the Caribbean Biological Corridor Initiative and propose them for the approval of the Ministerial Committee.
5. Promote, execute and/or coordinate the implementation of the Caribbean Biological Corridor Initiative, its work plans and projects, as well as monitor its execution in the first instance.
6. Ensure that the activities of the work plan are carried out diligently and efficiently and records, accurate and regular accounts, are kept on the implementation of said activities.
7. Within the framework of the powers conferred by the Ministerial Committee, follow up on agreements with other departments, governmental and non-governmental institutions, linked to the objectives and strategic activities of the CBC.
8. Prepare progress reports on the activities programmed in the agendas and work plans, with a complete detail of all the aspects of the implementation during the covered period, which allows establishing a comparison with the objective(s) achieved, as well as the means used and all expenses incurred, the expected and achieved results and details of the budget allocated for those actions.
9. Prepare the provisional agenda and organize the meetings of the Ministerial Committee and the Scientific-Technical Committee.

10. Prepare the reports of the meetings of the Ministerial Committee and the Scientific-Technical Committee and present them to the Signatory Parties for their approval.
11. Follow up on the recommendations and indications emanating from the meetings of the Ministerial Committee.
12. Promote and facilitate the coordination of efforts with the different governmental and non - governmental institutions/organizations, and regional entities in matters of environment and natural resources to achieve effective synergies for the implementation of the CBC Strategy in the Caribbean.
13. Promote the CBC before international organizations, as well as before regional and international events related to the objectives of this Corridor.

2.4.4 Focal points

To guarantee the implementation of the agreed actions, the CBC has focal points in each country. The Ministries of the Environment of each signatory country designate the focal points, whose function is to act as a link, consult and follow up on the actions carried out by the Secretariat. In some countries, two focal points are designated, one scientific-technical and one political, which facilitates the implementation of actions on the ground.

2.4.5 Supporting partner organizations

Additionally, the CBC also relies on associated organizations to achieve the implementation of actions. These organizations can be from the ministries of the environment or other government agencies, or from academic, civil society, or private sector organizations. UNEP is a special case, as it is formally invited as a permanent observer and in fact it functions as an implementing and supporting agency for the CBC Secretariat, in the search for financing, and in the implementation of projects.

Figure 1 shows the relationships between the different components of the CBC governance mechanism, where the Ministerial Committee stands out as the highest decision-maker, for which it relies on the Scientific-Technical Committee, the Secretariat and UNEP, who accompanies and supports it as requested. The Secretariat plays a central role in the coordination and implementation of the strategy, in close collaboration with the National Focal Points, who provide support, coordinate, and supervise the implementation of actions on the ground. ●

Figure 1: CBC governance mechanism

3

Conservation Priorities

3.1 CONSERVATION PRIORITIES OF THE CBC

A set of premises and criteria were defined that allowed the priority selection process to be carried out objectively¹. To apply the selection criteria, a rigorous information analysis process was followed². As fine filter objects, 139 species were selected and grouped into 14 conservation objects shown in Table 1. This list represents the species assemblages to which the highest priority should be devoted in the plan period to guarantee their effective protection and monitoring. However, it is recommended that the member countries of the CBC protect and monitor other species that were not on the list of highest priority, but that accumulate a high score, which will constitute a contribution to the objectives of the CBC. For a third group of species that meet some of the criteria, but have obtained a lower score, it is recommended to promote their conservation and monitoring as opportunities arise.

Table 1: Fine filter conservation priorities

Priority species or groups of species for conservation	Scientific name
Reef-building corals	<i>Acropora cervicornis</i> , <i>Acropora palmata</i> , <i>Montastraea (Orbicella) annularis</i> , <i>Montastraea (Orbicella) faveolata</i>
Sea turtles	<i>Chelonia mydas</i> , <i>Dermochelys coriacea</i> , <i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i> , <i>Caretta caretta</i>
Highly Endangered Sharks and Rays	<i>Rhincodon typus</i> , <i>Mobula birostris</i> , <i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i> , <i>Sphyrna mokarran</i> , <i>S. lewini</i> , <i>Pristis pristis</i> , <i>P. pectinata</i>
Endangered snapper and grouper	<i>Epinephelus itajara</i> , <i>Epinephelus morio</i> , <i>Epinephelus striatus</i> , <i>Lutjanus campechanus</i> , <i>Lutjanus cyanopterus</i> , <i>Mycteroperca interstitialis</i>
American eel (threatened oceanic migratory fish)	<i>Anguilla rostrata</i>
Threatened marine mammals	<i>Trichechus manatus</i> , <i>Physeter macrocephalus</i>
Highly endangered crocodiles	<i>Crocodylus acutus</i> (Hispaniola Lakes), <i>Crocodylus rhombifer</i> (Western Zapata Swamp, Cuba)
Bicknell's Thrush	<i>Catharus bicknelli</i>
Black-capped Petrel	<i>Pterodroma hasitata</i>
Highly Endangered Endemic Iguanas	<i>Cyclura ricordii</i> , <i>Cyclura collei</i> , <i>Cyclura stejnegeri</i>
Solenodonts	<i>Solenodon paradoxus</i> , <i>Solenodon cubanus (cuban Atopogale)</i>
Highly endangered amphibians	100 species. They are taken as CC indicator group
Critically endangered birds of prey	<i>Buteo ridgwayi</i> y <i>Chondrohierax wilsonii</i>
Endangered endemic Hutias (rodents)	<i>Geocapromys brownii</i> , <i>Mesocapromys angelcabrerai</i> , <i>Mesocapromys auritus</i> , <i>Plagiodontia aedium</i>

¹For more details, consult the document "Criteria for the Selection of Priority Objects for Conservation and Monitoring within the framework of the Caribbean Biological Corridor".

²For more details, consult the document "Selection of Priority Objects for Conservation and Monitoring within the framework of the Caribbean Biological Corridor", available at <http://cbcbio.org/documentos-estrategicos-programas-y-plans/>

As coarse filter conservation targets, four ecosystems or sets of ecosystems representative of the threatened ecoregions of the Caribbean were selected: Moist forests and pinewoods, dry forests and xerophytic shrublands, mangrove forests and coral reefs. Each one was spatially assessed to determine the highest priority sites for conservation, according to the chosen selection criteria (Figure 2).

The humid forests and pine forests extend mainly over the mountainous areas, although in some flat areas there are important remnants from the point of view of connectivity. Dry forests and xerophytic thickets form corridors associated with coastal areas that are present or, in the case of Hispaniola, that existed in recent geological times. Due to the differentiated palaeogeographical evolution of the Greater Antilles, the mangroves have an uneven geographical distribution. Cuba, with more than 5,000 km of coastline and more than 4,000 predominantly low-lying islands and keys, is home to more than 5,000 km² of mangroves, which represent more than 80% of all those existing in the area. They are followed in importance by those of Hispaniola, with barely 500 km². Finally, the coral reefs with the highest priority (very high) extend fundamentally in the south of Cuba (Gulf of Cazones and Jardines de la Reina) and in some patches of the western end and Sabana-Camagüey. They are also found in smaller patches in the Dominican Republic (Beata, Saona and north coast). Puerto Rico (Culebra). High priority patches are found in Haiti, but reefs in these categories are virtually absent in Jamaica. ●

Figure 2: Distribution of coarse filter priorities (ecosystems)

Additionally, other species are priorities for monitoring in the CBC, as they are indicator species of regional connectivity, including migratory birds of prey and passerines.

4

CBC

Design³

³A detailed explanation of the fundamental points of the CBC design can be found in the document Bases and Conceptual Model of the CBC

4.1 PREMISES FOR THE DESIGN

The design of the CBC was based on premises extracted from the documents generated by the initiative itself in the framework of its development since 2007:

1. Develop in a delimited geographical space.
2. Consider both the terrestrial and marine spheres in their delimitation and future expansion.
3. Prioritize the regional approach to conservation.
4. Provide connectivity, not only ecological but also social (provides connectivity between landscapes, ecosystems, habitats, and cultures).
5. Maintain biodiversity, ecological processes, and environmental services of regional importance.
6. Prioritize the conservation of biodiversity hotspots in the Insular Caribbean.
7. Promote actions to strengthen or restore climate resilience, promote adaptation based on ecosystems and natural solutions, as well as the reduction of vulnerability to the effects of climate change.
8. Promote sustainable development at the local level.
9. Work as a platform to promote synergies and South-South cooperation.
10. Be financially sustainable.

4.2 STRATEGIC CONCEPTUAL AXES

Five strategic conceptual axes associated with the essential functions of the CBC were defined, based on the premises emanating from the agreements of the Ministerial Committee meetings.

Axis 1: Maintenance of ecological connectivity through the conservation and restoration of key ecosystems

Nature sustains the healthy functioning of the planet, and therefore the health and existence of humanity itself. To keep ecosystems healthy, it is not enough to protect the remaining values of nature. It is necessary to ensure the continuity of natural processes, maintain ecosystem services, guarantee the sustainability of resource-use, and provide essential benefits for all people. This requires restoring or maintaining ecological connectivity.

To maintain ecological connectivity, both the conservation of natural landscapes and the promotion of connectivity processes in agricultural and productive landscapes and marine landscapes with productive socioeconomic uses must be ensured. The CBC should promote actions for the conservation or restoration of ecosystems that improve connectivity at all spatial scales and levels of biodiversity with a Ridge-to-Reef approach where relevant, although its fundamental approach it must be the maintenance of connectivity processes on a regional scale. The restoration actions in the CBC will be carried out as a direct contribution to the objectives of the United Nations Decade on Ecosystem Restoration, led by UNEP and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), which seeks to prevent, stop, and reverse the degradation of ecosystems around the world. It also aligns with Outcome 3 of the Action for Nature thematic sub-programme of the UNEP Mid-Term Strategy which, among other activities, promotes landscape-scale ecosystem restoration, complemented with social and behavioral changes, to minimize damage to valuable ecosystems.

▲ Ravine du Sud, river that connects Pic Macaya and Les Cayemites, in Haiti, presents the effect of sedimentation due to deforestation upstream.

Conservation of key sites for connectivity and ecological restoration to establish corridors in areas that have lost their connectivity function not only facilitate gene flow and the exchange of individuals between populations of priority species and ecosystems, but also help improve the resilience of ecosystems.

Axis 2: Effective conservation of the most representative and threatened values of the biodiversity of the insular Caribbean

It is essential to ensure that biodiversity is valued, conserved, restored, and used wisely. For this, it is necessary to protect, restore and monitor the most representative and resilient threatened ecosystems that are shared in the countries, and the populations of endemic species that are most threatened and vulnerable to climate change. This will be in line with the commitments made by the countries with the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals (CMS) and the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Fauna and Wild Flora (CITES). The work in this area will also contribute to the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals number 14 (Life Underwater) and 15 (Life in Terrestrial Ecosystems).

Axis 3: Strengthening resilience to climate change

Key ecosystems for the region, such as coral reefs, coastal wetlands, and montane moist forests, provide essential environmental services to human communities in the CBC, are home to priority species, and support regional connectivity. These ecosystems are highly vulnerable to climate change, and their resilience has

▲ Community members preparing bales of seagrass to feed manatees.

been compromised by processes not associated to climate. The impact of extreme weather events can trigger community pressures on biodiversity resources. The intensification of pressures on resources reduces the resilience of ecosystems, and with it the impacts of climate change are accentuated, thus starting a positive feedback loop. It is required to increase the capacity of human communities to adapt to the adverse impacts of climate change and foster climate resilience. Within the CBC, this will be fostered by promoting nature-based solutions (NBS), especially ecosystem-based adaptation (EbA).

Work in this strategic axis will be aligned with the commitments of the member countries with the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, and in particular those emanating from the Glasgow Pact, agreed at COP26. It will also contribute to the implementation within the CBC of the Climate Action thematic subprogram of the UNEP Mid-Term Strategy, and to Sustainable Development Goal number 13 Climate Action.

Axis 4: Sustainability of development in communities

In a complex economic and social context such as the one that frames the CBC initiative, where many local communities have limited livelihood alternatives, it is not possible to achieve effective conservation of biodiversity without solving the human development problems that lead to its degradation. The CBC promotes the concept that biodiversity conservation is an imperative for development, not only because of the inherent value and cultural significance of species and ecosystems, but also because of their past, present, and future contribution to society in areas that

are vital for the livelihoods of local communities, and the sustainable development of the Caribbean region. The actions promoted by the CBC must contribute to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), especially SDG 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16. It will also contribute to the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework with the ultimate objective of improving the human well-being and encouraging the implementation of sustainable development models.

Axis 5: Strengthening the capacity for governance, south-south cooperation and coordinated work between multiple actors and at multiple scales

Dealing effectively with environmental crises is only possible when actions are underpinned by sound environmental governance. Therefore, for the CBC it is of particular importance to work on the relationships between different users or actors related to biodiversity resources, governance systems, and the natural systems and associated resources. Without the coordinated participation of key actors, it is not possible to achieve the success of the policies and actions promoted by the initiative. The CBC promotes the application of science and recognizes that the use of data for monitoring and evaluation is a critical tool for decision making. Focusing on common goals, promoting South-South cooperation, ensuring the coordinated action of all key actors through constructive and cooperative social connectivity, as well as supporting decision-making with science, are obligations and challenges for the continuous and effective operation of the initiative.

Work on this axis aligns with and will contribute to the goals of UNEP's founding sub-programme on environmental governance, which seeks to work across regions and countries to strengthen effective environmental governance and the rule of law.

4.3 OBJECTIVES, MISSION, AND VISION

4.3.1 Objectives

The overall objective of the CBC Initiative is to build a strong, collectively sustained, institutional regional approach to the conservation and management of shared terrestrial and marine biodiversity of regional importance in the Caribbean islands, contributing to both global conservation and conservation. poverty reduction in the region.

The corridor's specific objectives are:

1. Ensure the effective conservation of marine and terrestrial biodiversity of regional importance and its ecological connectivity in key sites of the insular Caribbean.
2. Strengthen governance and the creation of effective cooperation networks at different levels, to achieve a sustainable socio-ecological relationship between the communities of resource users and the ecosystems that provide them.
3. Work within your geographic area to improve the resilience of ecosystems to climate change and promote ecosystem-based adaptation measures.

4.3.2 Mission

“Achieve the effective conservation of marine and terrestrial biodiversity of regional importance and the maintenance of ecological connectivity in key sites of the insular Caribbean, considering the challenges of a changing climate, the

needs of community development, and ensuring the coordination, integration, and cooperation of all relevant actors.”

The mission is designed to stimulate action and create the conditions for an environmentally sustainable future in the insular Caribbean, based on respecting for the functioning of ecosystems, the recognition of national needs for development, and the joint confrontation of shared challenges, promoting inclusive and transformative change in their field.

4.3.3 Institutional vision to 2030

“The CBC is a consolidated, financially sustainable and effective South-South cooperation initiative for the conservation of biodiversity of regional importance for the insular Caribbean, which ensures and monitors its ecological connectivity in key sites and promotes sustainable development in a context of changing climate”.

The vision is a statement of purpose and existence oriented to the future, which recognizes the responsibility of the countries to work in a coordinated way in favor of agreed objectives and to face common challenges.

4.3.4 Vision of the future to 2050

The CBC works to forge with actions in the present the hope of a better future. The vision of that hope is:

“An insular region where nature thrives alive, diverse, whole and healthy, and is used wisely, sustainably and harmoniously for the benefit of a Caribbean society that is heterogeneous, but peaceful, just, inclusive and prosperous”.

4.3.5 CBC values

Five values guide the performance of the CBC initiative and its Executive and Technical Secretariat; and constitute the foundation on which they rely to fulfill their mission, achieve their goals, and achieve their vision.

Integrity

Solidarity

Knowledge

Dedication

Effectiveness

INTEGRITY is part of the shared set of moral principles upheld by the people, who make up the CBC and its Executive and Technical Secretariat. Our collaborators are honest, upright, transparent, capable of listening, and tolerant and respectful of diversity. Respect for diversity means that we are fervent defenders of nature and its biological diversity, and that we also understand, respect, and defend the right of people and nations to cultural, political, creed, ethnic and gender diversity.

SOLIDARITY is one of the pillars of our initiative. We promote the well-being of people in the scope of action of the CBC, we promote the exchange of knowledge and cooperation in solving common problems, working together with those involved in the search for joint solutions with altruism and harmony.

KNOWLEDGE is the basis of all action in the CBC. It implies not only resorting to the best existing scientific-technical knowledge to fulfill our mission, also the traditional knowledge provided by local communities, as well as the constant search for the enrichment of knowledge, allows the fair and equitable distribution of benefits derived from them.

The members of the work teams in the CBC demonstrate **DEDICATION**. This means that we can devote ourselves to fulfilling the mission and the goals that are set, especially in times of crisis or tension.

Finally, all the previous values are not enough if the expected results are not achieved. That is why a central value of the CBC is **EFFECTIVENESS**; that is, the ability to work effectively to achieve the fulfillment of the mission and tasks. We deliver results with the expected quality and at the expected time, finding creative solutions to the problems that are faced.

4.4 CONCEPTUAL MODEL

4.4.1 CBC as a social-ecological system

The CBC is conceptualized as a complex social-ecological system (SES), in which not only the territorial units of biodiversity conservation that form an ecological network are interconnected, but also the actors that govern and use the resources, forming a social network.

Spatially, the CBC is made up of a territorial ecological network made up of conservation units, which are mainly terrestrial and marine protected areas, but also other area-based effective conservation measures (OECMs) of regional importance. These units are linked by corridors (terrestrial and marine) that guarantee the terrestrial and marine landscape ecological connectivity at different spatial scales and levels of biodiversity. In addition, the CBC includes large, unprotected swaths that are part of the matrix of terrestrial and marine landscapes with productive uses that help maintain regional ecosystem connectivity and the goods and services provided by ecosystems, through actions aimed at supporting conservation, promoting ecological restoration, and guaranteeing the sustainable use of resources. Superimposed on this territorial ecological network, there is a network of social actors from a wide range of institutions and sectors with diverse interests and roles, who protect the conservation units, monitor biodiversity, make decisions about, and establish rules to regulate how to protect and use biodiversity resources.

Therefore, the CBC goes beyond ecological connectivity, since its social network of actors (made up of decision-makers, authorities, civil society, the private sector, as well as users of natural resources) must struggle to meet the challenge of achieving a sustainable relationship between both networks (social and ecological). Figure 3 shows the conceptual model that details the structure of the networks that make up the CBC social-ecological system.

Figure 3: The CBC conceptual model

4.4.2 CBC as a platform for South-South cooperation

In order to implement its principles and achieve its objectives, and in accordance with its conceptual model, the CBC is conceived as a platform for south-south cooperation (as a social network) in which its fundamental principles and priorities are promoted (conservation of biodiversity, conservation or restoration of ecosystems and their ecological connectivity, the sustainability of the use of biodiversity resources and development in communities, and the strengthening of coordinated governance between multiple actors and at multiple scales) and everyone is invited to participate. who wishes to contribute, either with projects developed by the Secretariat or with the participation of the Secretariat, or with totally independent projects (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Model of the CBC as a platform for South-South cooperation

The Secretariat, together with UNEP, identifies financing opportunities and prepares and implements regional projects. Similarly, the CBC seeks to create partnerships and encourages its partners to identify funding opportunities, to develop and implement projects in a coordinated manner that respond to the priorities of the initiative. Finally, other actors can identify and develop totally independent projects that can be considered part of the initiative if they align with and contribute to the initiative's priorities.

In all cases, the projects must contribute directly to the strategic lines of the CBC; for which the Secretariat maintains a portfolio of project profiles where the issues identified as priorities are addressed.

4.5 DEMARCATION

The CBC demarcation (see Figure 5) occupies a total area of 142,007 km², of which 28,746 km² (20%) correspond to core areas and 113,261 km² (80%) to connectivity areas. Figure 6 (a and b) shows the distribution of the CBC by type of environment (land vs. sea), and by zones. Marine areas occupy 67% of the demarcation, of which almost 91% corresponds to connectivity zones, while in land environments the proportion of connectivity zones is 57%, and 43% corresponds to core conservation areas. The CBC have a notable contribution to the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework in land environment, which aspires to a minimum of 30% of the territories dedicated to conservation. In the marine environment, however, the restricted nature of the areas selected as core is proportionally much smaller, which is decisively influenced by the fact that in this study only coral reefs and specific sites of importance for connectivity were considered as regional priorities. A deeper analysis using additional criteria is possible to improve the marine demarcation of the CBC. The details of the demarcation can be explored in the CBC's BioAtlas tool, an online GIS application developed for this purpose.

Figure 5: New demarcation of the Caribbean Biological Corridor (2022)

Figure 6: a) Distribution of the demarcation by land/sea. b) Percentage distribution of the demarcation by CBC zone and land/sea

Table 2 shows the distribution of the demarcation by country. The Dominican Republic has the largest area of the CBC, covering 45% of the demarcation, followed by Cuba, with 34%. However, when observing the distribution by type of zones, Cuba has 48% of the core zones, seconded by the Dominican Republic with 37%. As expected, Haiti, Jamaica, and Puerto Rico have the least extension within the corridor's demarcation.

Distribution of the CBC demarcation by types of zones and countries (Areas in km²)

Zone/Countries (km ²)	Cuba	Haití	Rep. Dominicana	Puerto Rico	Jamaica	Total*
Core zones	13,912	1,312	10,605	954	1,950	28,732
% Core zones	48	5	37	3	7	100
Conectividad	34,829	5,828	53,568	5,323	12,228	111,777
% Conectividad zones	31	5	47	5	11	99
Total	48,741	7,140	64,173	6,277	14,178	140,508
% Demarcation	34	5	45	4	10	99

*Data on Navassa not included.

When analyzing the land demarcation in relation to the surface of each country (Table 3) values range from 11% in Puerto Rico to 35% in the Dominican Republic. The country with the highest proportion of core areas is the Dominican Republic, with 19%. Jamaica and Cuba follow (13% and 8%), while Puerto Rico and Haiti have 4% and 3% of their territory in core areas, respectively.

Table 3: Distribution of land demarcation by types of zones within each country (Area in km²)

Zones/ Countries/ (km ²)	Cuba	%	Haití	%	Rep. Dominicana	%	Puerto Rico	%	Jamaica	%	Total	% del CBC*
Core zones	8,256	8	905	3	9,169	19	355	4	1,426	13	20,111	14
Connec- tivity	13,319	12	2,962	11	7,995	16	644	7	1,684	15	26,603	19
Total	21,575	20	3,868	14	17,164	35	999	11	3,110	28	46,714	33

*Data on Navassa not included.

Table 4 shows the demarcation by zones and protected areas according to the categories of the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). Most of the demarcation (71%) is in protected areas and 56% in protected areas of restrictive management categories (IUCN categories I-IV). Moreover, 96% of the CBC core areas are in protected areas, and 71% in protected areas of restrictive management categories, which grants them greater legal protection, and provides a robust structure of core areas in the CBC.

Table 4: Demarcation by protected area category (Amounts cannot be obtained because there are overlapping areas in more than one category (Area in km²))

Zones/ UICN categories (km ²)	Cat I	Cat II	Cat III	Cat IV	Cat V	Cat VI	Fuera de AP	% en AP	% Cat I-IV
Core	774	21,190	1,235	4,889	2,341	6,555	1,223.4	96	71
Connectivity	32,590	1,5624	704	19,121	2,539	9,471	39,390	65	52
Total	33,364	36,814	1,939	24,010	4,880	16,026	40,613.2	71	56
% protected	32.9	36.3	1.9	23.7	4.8	15.8			

Table 5 shows the areas of the demarcation by type of priority. Of the priority ecosystems, the moist forests and pinewoods are the ones that contribute the most to the new demarcation in terms of surface, followed by dry forests and shrublands, coral reefs and finally mangroves. It should be considered that the values in the table add up to more than the area of the current demarcation, since there are overlaps in some of the areas considered in the analysis of the demarcation. The areas occupied by land species that are conservation priorities and that do not overlap with the distribution of priority ecosystems cover more than 18,500 km², while the areas to complement terrestrial connectivity cover about 13,400 km². Contrasting with this is the fact that the marine connectivity completion areas occupy 101,843 km² (49% of the total demarcation).

The demarcation of the CBC is not static, and its review cycle must start at least every three years. This review includes not only the changes that are obviously necessary due to the new thematic and spatial priorities that were agreed upon, but also those that become necessary as new countries and territories join the initiative.

Table 5: Zones by type of priority

CBC zones	Type of priority (km ²)													
	Coarse filter conservation targets				Fine filter conservation targets					Complementary areas for the corridor design				
	Moist forest & pinewood	Dry forest & xerophytic shrublands	Mangrove	Coral reefs	Species conservation targets	Concentration of migratory birds	Bird nesting areas	Sea turtle nesting areas	Reef fish spawning aggregations	Core land area completion	Core marine area completion	Land connectivity completion	Marine connectivity completion	Total
Core	12,387	6,433	5,907	4,623	8,392	872	84	105	420	857	354	0	0	40,434
Connectivity	9,926	8,728	3,201	8,858	10,167	2,301	41	15	765	0	0	13,428	101,843	159,269
Total	22,313	15,161	9,108	13,481	18,559	3,173	125	116	1,185	857	354	13,428	101,843	199,703

4.6 EXPECTED BENEFITS OF THE CBC

The CBC is expected to provide benefits to biodiversity, as well as to local communities and authorities responsible for the policies and management of biodiversity resources. The benefits of the CBC justify the need for its existence in member countries, by the provision of services and opportunities, and the contribution to goals and objectives that go beyond national visions. The main potential benefits identified are:

1. The CBC enables the agreement of a regional vision on shared values of biodiversity, ecosystem services, problems, and priorities, as well as developing a regional strategy for joint, coordinated, and responsible action.
2. The CBC supports the development of a network of interconnected conservation areas that allows ecosystems and populations of priority species to be effectively protected for their long-term survival.
3. The CBC supports the development of a network of areas where natural infrastructure is protected or restored to maintain connectivity and key habitats, in a way that guarantees the functioning of ecosystems, the adequate flow of matter and migratory species, as well as the exchange of individuals and genes between wild populations that would otherwise be isolated.
4. The effective management of the CBC ecological network contributes to guaranteeing the continuous provision of goods and services by ecosystems, and to achieving the long-term sustainability of the livelihoods of the local communities that depend on biodiversity resources.

5. The CBC helps improve the integrity and connectivity of ecosystems, and the effective protection and conservation of wild species and their genetic diversity.
6. The CBC promotes key terrestrial and marine ecosystems to be under spatial, multisectoral and integrated planning to guarantee environmental sustainability.
7. The CBC provides member countries with the only sub-regional governance mechanism dedicated to the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity of regional importance, both marine and terrestrial.
8. The CBC allows maintaining a regional system for monitoring species and ecosystems, as key indicators of the health of biodiversity, with emphasis on its connectivity, which facilitates decision-making processes between countries and adaptive management.
9. The CBC maintains an Integrated Knowledge Management System (IKMS) that provides member countries with relevant information, analytical services, and a set of tools to share and analyze information for regional decision-making.
10. The CBC provides an accepted platform for channeling and ensuring south-south cooperation in biodiversity conservation and sustainable development at the sub-regional level that allows for more efficient use of regional expertise and helps find viable solutions to environmental problems common to all countries, contributing to a more rational and effective use of the technical resources of those involved in the initiative.
11. The CBC provides member countries with a successful and proven effective platform to jointly seek and secure funds to address shared priorities on biodiversity conservation and sustainable development, acting at regional, national, and local scales through projects of subregional scope, and closing the gap between the necessary and available resources to achieve its Vision, which is an approach prioritized by many financing and cooperation agencies.
12. The CBC promotes and helps member countries to accounting for the contributions that nature makes to their economies to support relevant decisions with this information.
13. The CBC helps and supports the member countries of the initiative in fulfilling their commitments to the Multilateral Environmental Agreements to which they are a party, especially the Agreements of the Forum of Ministers of Latin America and the Caribbean, the Convention on Biological Diversity's Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework, and the commitments emanating from the Glasgow Climate Summit, as well as other commitments on biodiversity, climate change and sustainable development within the framework of the United Nations 2030 agenda or regional agreements.
14. The CBC promotes and helps implement new sustainable and gender-sensitive alternatives for the comprehensive development of local communities in key

sites and contributes to the long-term sustainability of nature-based livelihoods and enterprises.

- 15.** The CBC helps businesses that depend on biodiversity or that may affect biodiversity in key sites for the initiative to identify values to protect, learn about and implement best practices, and prepare to certify their products and services with sustainability labels.
- 16.** The CBC helps create local capacities to restore relationships between people and nature and for sustainable local development with equity.
- 17.** The CBC helps improve the resilience of ecosystems and communities to climate change by finding alternatives that reduce non-climate pressures on biodiversity and implementing nature-based solutions and other adaptation measures that are timely and appropriate. ●

▶ Parrotfish
(*Sparisoma
viride*) in coral
reefs of the
Greater Antilles.

A sea turtle with a patterned shell and head is swimming in a clear blue ocean. The background is filled with various types of coral, including branching and feathery varieties. The lighting is bright, highlighting the textures of the turtle's skin and the surrounding marine life.

5

Problem Analysis (Diagnosis)

5.1 CONSERVATION ISSUES

5.1.1 Threat analysis of conservation targets

A diagnosis of the state of conservation and main threats that are affecting the CBC priorities has been carried out, applying the principles of the methodology of the Open Standards for the Practice of Conservation developed by the Conservation Measures Partnerships⁴ (CMP, 2020). For the evaluation, a review of the information available on the state of conservation and main threats to the priorities of the CBC was carried out, based on the information available in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (IUCN, 2021) and numerous scientific papers and technical reports available on the Internet⁵.

Twenty-three direct threats to conservation targets were documented and described of which 11 were assessed as Critical due to their scope, intensity, and irreversibility, all shared by one or more targets:

1. The indiscriminate clearing of forests
2. Selective clearing of high value hardwood species.
3. Wildfires
4. Overfishing
5. Bycatch
6. The impacts of fishing gear on ecosystems and species
7. Introduced, invasive and/or predatory species
8. Infrastructure development and urbanization
9. Pollution
10. Illegal hunting, take or collection of wild species
11. Climate change

Next, the chains of factors that lead to these critical threats are described, which in some cases have been grouped due to the close relationship between them.

Indiscriminate forest clearing: In many rural areas, one of the factors that leads to this threat is the demand and production of charcoal and firewood due to the limited options for domestic fuel, as the main source of energy for the daily activities carried out by the communities. It is also largely due to unsustainable agricultural practices and the use of biodiversity resources with the advance of livestock areas and permanent agriculture as a result of the high demand of produces and dairy products, and because of the limited livelihood alternatives of rural communities. Added to this is the effect of insufficient surveillance capacity and weak enforcement of regulations. Among the driving forces leading to this situation are: i) the forces of national and international market, ii) limited availability of financial resources, iii) weak production and value chains linking local and global levels, iv) lack of knowledge, training, and environmental awareness and, v) poverty in general.

⁴The CMP is an association of conservation-oriented NGOs, government agencies, and funding organizations working collectively for better methods to design, manage, and measure the impacts of conservation actions and to learn about and improve conservation efforts.

⁵A detailed description of the methodology and results of the conservation diagnosis can be found in the CBC Scientific-Technical Report "Diagnosis of the Conservation Problem of the CBC Priorities and Possible Actions", available at www.cbcbio.org.

▲ Whale shark (*Rhincodon typus*).

Selective clearing of high-value hardwood species: This is produced by the demand of precious wood and timber for commercial use, encouraged by the demand generated by national and export trade, both legal and illegal, as well as by the limited livelihood alternatives in rural areas.

Wildfires: Although not all land priority ecosystems are equally prone to the impacts of fire; all are, in one way or another, affected by this threat. Fires are caused both by natural causes (lightning and friction of branches) and by the insufficient surveillance and enforcement capacity of agencies, which hamper their ability to effectively protect the forests from poachers, collectors of firewood and other resources, tree cutters, and the general movement of people. These people often cause fires due to carelessness (e.g. cigarettes and poorly extinguished campfires). Sometimes fires are provoked as a traditional practice for clearing areas for farming (slash-and-burn agriculture). Prolonged droughts facilitate the accumulation of flammable materials leading to larger fires. Early warning and wildfire fighting systems are generally weak, an important factor in the spreading of wildfires with a high impact on biodiversity.

Overfishing, bycatch and impact of fishing gear: These threats occur due to the application of unsustainable fishing practices which, in turn, are due to a set of factors such as limited livelihood alternatives; lack of knowledge, training and environmental awareness; the existence of legal gaps and perverse incentives for fishing; as well as weak surveillance and enforcement capacity for the protection of key areas. The limited availability of financial resources and poverty are driving forces behind these factors.

▲ American redstart (*Setophaga ruticilla*).

Introduced, invasive and/or predatory species: Population growth and agricultural expansion have led to the spread of invasive introduced species, which compete with or prey on native species. In the marine environment, shipping and transit of other vessels might contribute to the dispersion of exotic species and diseases in marine ecosystems, mainly by means of racking and dumping of bilge and ballast waters.

Infrastructure development, urbanization, mining, and associated pollution: The first two factors are caused above all by the insufficient capacity for adequate and environmentally friendly coastal development and the insufficient capacity for monitoring and application of regulations by the agencies in charge. The lack of economic incentives for sustainable practices further pushes producers to focus on short-term production strategies, or farmers in vulnerable positions to seek other profitable alternatives such as illegal artisanal mining of gold and other precious minerals; while industrial open pit mining of nickel, bauxite and other ores is growing in some of the CBC countries, fragmenting the landscape and contributing to water pollution. The regions with accumulation of heavy metals in soils generally constitute centers of evolution of endemic species; therefore, open pit mineral extraction at these sites has the potential to become one of the main drivers of the extinction of endemic species. Pollution occurs from both land and marine sources and affects several of the CBC's priority ecosystems and species. The direct disposal in the sea of litter, fuels and lubricants, sewage, bilge and ballast water and other pollutants are produced by the transit of ships and boats that sustain shipping, fishing, tourism, and maritime recreational activities. Many other pollutants are produced in land-based facilities, primarily from urban centers, agricultural plantations, and tourist development zones.

The abuse in the use of some compounds and materials, the lack of measures to avoid pollution, single-use plastic articles, and the deficient systems for the collection, separation, reuse, recycling and treatment of waste and contaminants lead to a high impact. It is necessary to work both with those responsible for waste management and with producers and consumers to reduce the demand and impact of some polluting materials and compounds. Of particular concern are plastics, especially those for single use by the tourism industry, one of the development engines in Caribbean countries. The lack of knowledge, training and environmental awareness is a factor that also influences the situation. Mining can also become one of the main sources of pollution with consequences from the mountains to the reefs (Ridge-to-Reef) due to the extensive use and dumping of toxic substances in freshwater currents during the separation of heavy metals from soil and sediments. The driving forces behind these chains of factors are population growth, unsustainable development policies, and the growth of tourism and mining in natural areas.

Illegal hunting, take or collection of wildlife: The limited surveillance and enforcement capacity in key areas is one of the factors contributing to this threat, together with the existence of some legal gaps and the demand of biodiversity products in black-markets. Some products have a high value in the international black-market (e.g. tortoiseshell). In some areas there is a local tradition of consuming endangered species or their parts, also driven by limited food alternatives. Some species are sometimes in demand as pets (as is the case of songbirds and some reptiles); but in other cases, consumption is encouraged by false beliefs and popular myths about alleged aphrodisiac powers or high nutritional value (as is the case of sea turtle eggs and meat or manatee meat). In these cases, the limited availability of financial funds; restricted livelihood alternatives; lack of knowledge, training, and environmental awareness; and poverty are driving forces that lead to this direct threat.

Climate change: There is consensus that current climate change is produced essentially by the global warming resulting of the excessive emissions of greenhouse gases from diverse anthropogenic sources. Among them, greenhouse gases from fossil fuel combustion stands out, but other activities such as deforestation and cattle raising account for an important share in emissions, while contribute to the loss of carbon sinks.

5.1.2 Analysis of the problems of rural communities that affect nature conservation

Effective conservation of nature and its biodiversity cannot be achieved if the problems of human communities that depend on the resources and services provided by ecosystems are not addressed. For this reason, an analysis of threats and barriers preventing rural communities in the CBC to be healthy, resilient, and sustainable was carried out.

Three fundamental elements directly threaten the sustainable, healthy, and resilient development of rural communities in the CBC geographic scope: The degradation of the capacity of ecosystems to provide renewable resources and environmental services, the vulnerability of local communities to climate change, and their high socioeconomic vulnerability. These three factors are conditioned by a complex chain of driving forces and intermediate factors.

One of the factors that in the first instance contributes to this situation is the predominance of unsustainable practices of resource use, including indiscriminate deforestation to advance the agricultural frontier and to produce firewood and charcoal, migratory slash-and-burn agriculture, overgrazing on slopes, overfishing, and intensive use of agrochemicals in some areas. Other factors are the high dependence that communities have on fragile ecosystems that are sensitive to climate change, their high exposure to extreme events, the lack of adequate adaptation measures, and the limited availability of qualified human resources.

These, in turn, are conditioned by a second level of indirect factors, which include limited livelihood alternatives, lack of knowledge and information leading to limited environmental awareness and weak community institutions; the lack of job opportunities that causes migration to urban areas, and the lack of satisfaction of basic needs. All of this is the consequence of a group of root causes that includes limited sources of financing and poverty; the predominance of a short-term vision that favors prioritizing quick-return productions, leading to policies that do not encourage sustainable rural development and that prioritize technified monoculture projects and high chemicalization; the little availability of fair market opportunities, the limited value chains and weak productive linkages; and the existence of vulnerable social groups. The conceptual model of these chains of factors is shown in Annex II: Factors that threaten the development of healthy, resilient and sustainable communities.

In the analysis of threats to conservation targets and communities, possible strategic actions were identified, and result chains were developed. This helped developing the Theory of Change and the Logical Framework that support the actions proposed in this plan.

5.1.3 Main CBC conservation and restoration gaps

The main gaps recognized for the current demarcation of the CBC are related to the acknowledged limitations of the priority selection process and that consequently were carried over into the definition of the current demarcation. In the marine domain, for example, seagrasses could not be included in the analyzes carried out due to the lack of adequate mapping, while deep-sea ecosystems in general are poorly represented in protected area systems and current CBC demarcation. In the case of land areas, there was not enough spatial information available to analyze the threatened flora, and freshwater ecosystems are only indirectly represented. Priority areas for restoration have not been identified nor are they part of the current demarcation. It is therefore required, as a basic task for the implementation of this plan, to carry out a systematic analysis of the conservation and restoration gaps in the CBC demarcation that guides the actions to strengthen the conservation and restoration network of the initiative.

5.1.4 Main knowledge gaps on biodiversity of regional importance

The main issues in which there are still gaps in knowledge or fundamental information on biodiversity, and which should be considered in prioritizing actions in the CBC are:

1. Analysis of the priorities for the restoration of marine, coastal, terrestrial, and freshwater landscapes and ecosystems in the CBC.

2. Analysis of representativeness and regional connectivity of ecosystems and priority species to determine conservation gaps and propose modifications to the protected areas and OECM of the CBC, as well as analysis of the effectiveness of protection and management measures.
3. Basic studies on biodiversity.
4. Connectivity studies at different scales.
5. Studies on the spatial distribution of biodiversity and its threats.
6. Research and monitoring of the impact of climate change on Caribbean biodiversity and ecosystem services, and its implications for human communities.
7. Study, testing and systematic use of new technologies for the inventory, monitoring and investigation of wildlife and its threats, which help create robust monitoring and surveillance systems for key indicators for decision-making.
8. Valuation of ecosystem services and the contributions of nature to society and of society to conservation in the CBC.

5.2 INSTITUTIONAL AND FINANCIAL PROBLEMS

5.2.1 Legal framework of the initiative and institutional situation of the Secretariat

The Declaration of Santo Domingo, which gave rise to the CBC, is not legally binding, but it is recognized as a document that contains objectives and rights without necessarily implying a commitment by the States. It is a legal instrument that materializes the will of the governments to work together for the conservation of the biodiversity of the Caribbean and that has been implemented by the manifest will of the governments parties and is recognized internally in the different governments. The legal consequences of a declaration of this nature present various opportunities and limitations for the operation of its Executive Secretariat, in terms of its legal capacity to represent, be represented, and acquire rights and obligations.

The Inter-ministerial Agreement of the Caribbean Biological Corridor of 2014, although not binding either, has the quality of being an Agreement (the previous ones were declarations of political will). This not only reaffirms the commitment to the initiative, but also for the first time a document with legal format defines and supports several core aspects of the CBC:

- Its institutional structure.
- The functions of the different organs that comprise the aforementioned structure.
- The mechanism for the incorporation of new countries and territories to the initiative.
- The mechanism for revising the CBC demarcation.

This legal framework has not been updated, so it has outdated sections and there are obvious legal gaps around decisions of great importance. For example, the demarcation of the CBC is approved as a decision of the CBC Ministerial Committee, but it has no other international legal protection, nor is there a specific legal framework within the CBC member states that protects the demarcation of the CBC. Furthermore, the legislation regarding biological corridors in the member states is poorly developed.

◀ Mangroves,
Dominican
Republic.

Despite the legal limitations of the 2014 Inter-Ministerial Agreement, the member countries recognize the governance structure of the CBC, the consolidation achieved by the initiative in recent years, and the role that UNEP has played in this process, not only by support the achievement and management of financial resources to implement its action plan and for the operation of the Secretariat, but rather in the support given to the CBC in terms of transparency, proper management of resources and accountability, aspects that have contributed to the success of the implemented activities and projects.

Although different alternatives have been identified to ensure a legal personality for the CBC initiative and its Executive Secretariat, each with advantages and disadvantages⁶, the member countries agree that the problems of sustainability of the CBC initiative, rather than being related to legal personality, are essentially related to financial sustainability. For this reason, despite the existing legal gaps, the system used to date, which is based on the structure of UNEP for the operation of the Executive Secretariat and the transparent and responsible management of the funds obtained, has been efficient and decisive in the consolidation of the CBC. However, work should be done to update and strengthen the legal framework of the initiative, and to formalize UNEP's support for the Secretariat and the initiative, beyond the intervention based solely on project implementation.

5.2.2 Analysis of financial capacity

Until now, the CBC has been operating based on international cooperation projects and donations in kind from the ministries involved, the latter basically in the form of a fund of time dedicated by some employees to the activities of the CBC and the implementation of some activities in the field. From 2012 to 2021 the CBC has had a budget of approximately €800,000 per year (not counting the years without projects), which includes the creation and operations of the Secretariat and the regional and national programs⁷. The estimated baseline annual budget for the CBC Secretariat, including the organization of annual technical and ministerial meetings and the maintenance of technical functions and services, has been estimated at \$330,000 annually. An additional annual budget to support essential ecological monitoring actions and other technical tasks amounts to \$120,000, bringing the total annual core financial needs for the CBC to \$450,000. To achieve current CBC expenditures under EU funding, at least an additional \$550,000 in funding for project implementation on the ground would be desirable. Significant growth in funding for action on the ground is likely to result in an increase in the Secretariat's operating costs for managing larger projects and a larger number of projects.

A set of options have been identified to meet the CBC's annual financial needs listed above:

- Establish one or more endowment (trust) funds that generate enough interest to at least meet the basic needs of the initiative, while also enhancing its ability to seek additional funds for projects on the ground. As these funds grow and yield more

⁶A detailed description of the analysis carried out on the institutional framework of the initiative and the alternatives identified can be found in the Technical Consulting Report: "Institutional and Legal Arrangements for the Caribbean Biological Corridor (CBC)", available at www.cbcbio.org.

⁷A complete analysis of the problems of financial capacity can be found in the document: "Financial Strategy of the Caribbean Biological Corridor", available at www.cbcbio.org

benefits, increasing amounts can be dedicated to the implementation of priority actions without having to resort to submitting project proposals to calls made by different donors.

- Expand donors and bilateral and multilateral partners with complementary objectives to generate the necessary financing to implement projects that allow the implementation of the Strategic Plan of the initiative during the period of five to ten years that could be required to generate sustainable financial flows in the longer term. described in the previous point.
- Implementation of other innovative financing channels such as:
 - Apply direct charges for management and collection of some general costs to other regional and bilateral projects associated with the CBC. These fees would be variable but could be between \$50,000 and \$150,000 depending on the duration and scale of the co-managed projects.
 - Generate crowd-funding mechanisms with and without incentives.

5.2.3 Synthesis of the institutional problem: SWOT analysis

A SWOT analysis carried out⁸ allowed the identification of 13 Strengths, 19 Weaknesses, 14 Opportunities and 15 Threats for the CBC. Most of the Weaknesses and Strengths identified are related to structure, operation, and results, followed in importance (in the case of Strengths) by those of an institutional and organizational nature. The most frequently identified threats are related to the institutional and socioeconomic context and are followed in frequency by historical factors. As for the opportunities, the most frequently mentioned are of a political, financial, and institutional nature.

Of the 19 weaknesses identified, seven were weighted as the most significant according to their impact on strengths and threats:

1. Lack of financial sustainability: The initiative lacks a long-term financial sustainability mechanism in place, so it depends for its funding on ad hoc projects, which often have insufficient national counterparts. The projects depend on calls and financiers whose objectives are not necessarily aligned with the needs identified in the CBC, which is why they are not always accessible or imply tactical sacrifices in order to access funds. The lack of financial autonomy also implies that the Secretariat has to invest a lot of time to ensure financing through projects, while at the same time making it difficult to carry out effective medium and long-term planning to address the problems identified with the necessary resources. Additionally, lacking stable financing undermines the long-term enrollment of the Secretariat's technical staff and the continuity of the implementation of actions at the local and regional level. Another weakness pointed out, the lack of legal personality of the Secretariat also contributes to limiting its possibilities of taking advantage of financing opportunities, contributing in turn to the lack of financial sustainability.

⁷Complete analysis of the financial capacity problems is found in the document: Financial Strategy of the Caribbean Biological Corridor, available at https://cbbio.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/ES_Estrategia-Financiera-del-CBC-Approved.pdf

⁸See the document SWOT Analysis of the CBC initiative: A diagnostic element for the CBC Strategic Action Plan to 2031 for a detailed explanation of the analysis process and its findings.

- 2. The lack of formal arrangements with key actors:** The CBC lacks clear formal agreements with many key actors who develop coordinated or independent projects or are potential partners to implement actions. These agreements are necessary to establish the roles and relationships between the Secretariat and its partners, in a way that guarantees the contribution of these partners and projects to the CBC objectives, as well as the logistical and financial support to the Secretariat and the CBC governance system. This also hampers the supporting role the CBC Secretariat could play to help ensuring good performance of these projects. Additionally, the CBC lacks a strategy for rapprochement, articulation and coordination with other organizations interested in supporting the CBC. For example, a table of organizations that participate in the CBC (“Friends of the CBC”) could be organized to promote and facilitate the coordination of these actors that work in the CBC space; or a table of donors for regional actions within the scope of the CBC (including international organizations, the private sector and civil society). The lack of legal personality of the Secretariat also contributes to the fact that the agreements it signs are not binding, which sometimes limits their scope.
- 3. Insufficient communication on the CBC:** The CBC needs an intense dynamic of multilevel communication. In fact, some of the threats identified are related to the insufficient communication that is broadcasted about the CBC, both through mass media (TV, radio, etc.), and on its website and social network tools, although the latter shows progress. The existing logistical and technical mechanisms for updating the website and its associated tools are still inefficient and slow. There are different target audiences (for example, children, digital illiterates) and information technologies (radio, television, flat press) that are still little explored or used by the initiative; and without a wide dissemination of the importance and benefits of the CBC it is difficult to strengthen local cooperation and create expectations in potential partners to associate with the initiative. Although the current project has a communication strategy in implementation, greater dynamism and effectiveness is required.
- 4. The limited intervention at the local level:** The action of the CBC in local communities and priority areas has been limited. The CBC needs to implement high-impact projects at the local level that contribute to regional goals, obtaining not only funds for its own projects, but also through alliances with strategic partners that explicitly contribute to the objectives of the CBC at the local level. On-the-ground projects are an effective way to stimulate actions that contribute to reducing pressure on natural resources in key areas for the initiative.
- 5. The limited results of the IKMS and poor communication infrastructure:** In general, the initiative lacks a broad and efficient communication technology infrastructure that allows remote joint work throughout the CBC, which has become an urgent need in the framework of the COVID-19 pandemic. On the other hand, the CBC’s Integrated Knowledge Management System (IKMS) still does not systematically generate all the products or services needed to support decisions, and still does not fully help to improve the efficiency of work in the CBC. It is urgent to continue strengthening the IKMS and to provide the planned services with quality and efficiency.

6. The weak incorporation of the marine theme: The CBC has since 2014 the ministerial mandate to incorporate the marine realm in its demarcation and action. However, so far, the projects have not incorporated it and therefore no specific actions have been carried out in this area. It is important that in the new stage projects specifically aimed at the marine-coastal area are developed.

7. Insufficient number of staff in the Secretariat: The number of full-time technical staff in the Secretariat is not sufficient to cover the mass of tasks it faces, given the complexity of the scientific-technical and coordination functions carried out by this body of the CBC. The number of tasks is expected to grow in the future by increasing the territorial scope of the initiative, the number of projects and the number of partners to work with. On the other hand, there is a lack of young staff who can be trained and take over in the future.

Of the 15 Threats identified, eight were weighted as the most significant because they were the least attenuated by the strengths and the most concomitant with the weaknesses:

1. Insufficient will for local cooperation: Some local and national organizations highly value their institutional interest and are reluctant to collaborate transparently within the framework of initiatives such as the CBC. The initiative is still viewed with suspicion in some territories that do not perceive it as a valid or necessary forum.

2. Potential and real impact of extreme events and climate change: In a context of high vulnerability to climate change and other extreme events, phenomena such as hurricanes, epidemics, earthquakes, and others with a slow effect associated with climate change impact the implementation of projects by delaying the schedules and hamper work on the ground, limit resources, affect the availability of international funding, and shift national priorities.

3. Deforestation, fragmentation, and human occupation of the landscape: Many areas of importance for the preservation of the biodiversity of the CBC have a high population density and are affected by processes of deforestation, fragmentation, and transformation of the landscape. Associated with them are the overexploitation of resources, the loss of biological diversity and its ecological connectivity, accelerated erosion, the effects on water supply basins and the alteration of coastal ecosystems.

4. Competition for natural resources: Economic sectors that depend on the use of natural resources are interested in growing and compete for the use of common resources. This increases pressures on biodiversity resources, produces use conflicts, and can add stress to local livelihoods, which makes it more difficult to achieve conservation objectives.

5. High Transportation and Mobility Costs in the Caribbean: Transportation costs in the Caribbean are high. The islands are not always well connected to each other, nor do

▲ CBC expedition in El Morro National Park, Montecristi, Dominican Republic.

they have agreements that facilitate travel without complicated visa processes. This is a limitation for the development of a subregional initiative such as the CBC.

6. Lack of knowledge and little interest in CBC: Several potential key players and the general population have little knowledge of CBC and its potential benefits. This represents a serious limitation for the expansion of the initiative at the local level and achieve greater involvement of key actors in activities that contribute to the objectives of the initiative.

7. Geographical extension and fragmentation of the Caribbean: The Caribbean covers a wide geographical extension, while its insular condition and natural and anthropogenic fragmentation negatively impact the effectiveness of conservation efforts and resilience building at the local and regional levels by raising the transaction costs.

8. Political changes and instability: Changes in political portfolios affect the initiative by changes in the priorities of governments and their personnel. Of special concern is the political and social instability in Haiti, which delays the implementation of actions on the ground and smooth communication. This instability and changes place the CBC at certain times in unfavorable situations.

Of the 13 Strengths identified, seven were strategic for favoring Opportunities and being essential to reduce the impact of Threats on the initiative:

- 1. Commitment of foundational countries:** The environment ministers, other areas of these ministries and other ministries in the countries support the CBC initiative, both politically and technically, actively participate in the identification of projects and define technical and financial support.
- 2. Long-term strategy in development:** The initiative has the will and decision to promote and guide its long-term development through a strategy and plan. The strategy aims to build significant links between the conservation of biodiversity and its connectivity, the livelihoods of communities and the reduction of poverty, through the implementation of activities in protected areas and communities.
- 3. Flexibility in the participation approach:** The initiative facilitates participation through multiple projects reconciled with key actors and under different arrangements or even through independent projects. This will make it possible to gradually increase the agreed projects, to form a small core group of stakeholders that works closely and in coordination with the Secretariat, establishing terms of reference for this cooperation.
- 4. Strong CBC-UNEP alliance:** The UNEP Regional Office for Latin America and the Caribbean supports the initiative and has allowed the Secretariat to be institutionally represented in a neutral manner and help sustain it through projects. UNEP also offers support with its communication infrastructure and technical capacity.
- 5. Willingness to form alliances:** The initiative has the will to establish alliances with a high spirit of cooperation. This is vital to achieve the involvement and contribution of civil society organizations, the private sector and academia, in field actions on a wide spectrum of issues.
- 6. South-South cooperation platform:** The CBC has created the foundations and is willing to function as a platform for South-South cooperation and to build a regional strategy, opening the possibility for other countries to join the initiative. The CBC has been considered a model of south-south cooperation, first, for the conservation of biodiversity, but also for sustainable development, the search for peace and the implementation of operational initiatives that seek to improve the living conditions of the populations of the member countries. In an outstanding way, the CBC has made it possible to give priority to the support of Haiti by its neighbors Cuba and the Dominican Republic, providing technical assistance for the management of its biodiversity and the training of its people. In this sense, the CBC also helps to raise awareness in the region about the importance and role of biodiversity conservation in the Caribbean and the sustainability of the communities in its area.
- 7. Solid and decentralized Secretariat:** With high professional quality, experience, dedication, representativeness by country, which is perceived as a decentralized and independent entity from the environment ministries, but which works for the priorities of the countries.

From the 14 Opportunities identified, nine were weighted as strategic because they are reinforced by strengths and not hindered by weaknesses.

- 1. CBF's willingness to cooperate:** The Caribbean Biodiversity Fund (CBF) is recognized as a growing and reliable fund that has demonstrated its willingness to serve as a long-term financial mechanism for the CBC.
- 2. Developed and more accessible ICTs:** Advances in ICTs allow today to dramatically improve real-time communication and the extensive use of computer technologies for the dissemination of knowledge. In the COVID-19 pandemic, this has made it possible to intensify its use and redesign many activities that were previously face-to-face to do them remotely. This is also an effective way to reduce the CBC carbon footprint and reduce the costs of running the initiative efficiently.
- 3. Biological corridors priority:** The Post 2020 Global Biodiversity Framework and other regional and global platforms and strategies give biological corridors a high priority.
- 4. Mechanisms to give legal personality to the CBC Secretariat:** There are various mechanisms that can be explored to ensure that the CBC Secretariat has its own legal personality. For example, through the law of public-private partnerships in the Dominican Republic, a separate legal entity of a mixed nature could be created that could later be established in the rest of the countries.
- 5. Agency and donor interest in the CBC:** Both UNEP and the EU and other organizations have shown their interest in continuing to cooperate with the CBC.
- 6. Calls for projects:** Various donors regularly make calls for projects on relevant topics that can allow the continuity of the work of the CBC in the immediate future through projects. It is required to follow up and apply with proposals reconciled with the countries and partners.
- 7. Willingness of universities and other academic organizations:** There is a willingness in various academic institutions to support the development of research and postgraduate courses on topics of interest to the CBC.
- 8. Willingness to promote South-South cooperation:** The UN and other intergovernmental and bilateral cooperation organizations prioritize promoting South-South cooperation, one of the pillars of the CBC.
- 9. Interest in aligning national bodies and agencies:** Several national bodies and agencies that manage projects under implementation have shown interest in aligning themselves with the CBC, with which synergies and multiplier effects can be sought. ●

6

Strategic Program

6.1 THEORY OF CHANGE

To define the theory of change, we started from the diagnosis, the possible action strategies identified, and the general chain of results developed, and an attempt has been made to complement and support the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. It is based on the mission, objectives, milestones, and goals of the Post-2020 Global Framework for Biological Diversity, considers the strategy for Latin America of the European Union Beyond Jaguars, as well as the goals and objectives of the Caribbean Community (CARICOM) Strategy for the implementation of the Global Strategic Plan for Biological Diversity of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) until 2022 and beyond. Similarly, the Theory of Change is expected to be relevant and contribute to the UNEP Mid-Term Strategy.

The goal of the Strategic Plan is to help make the Caribbean an insular region where nature remains alive, diverse, whole and healthy, and is used wisely, sustainably and harmoniously for the benefit of a heterogeneous but peaceful Caribbean society, fair, inclusive and prosperous. For this, it is necessary to ensure that the CBC constitutes a consolidated, financially sustainable, and effective South-South cooperation initiative for the conservation of biodiversity of regional importance for the insular Caribbean, which ensures and monitors its ecological connectivity in key sites and promotes the development sustainable in a context of changing climate.

The diagnosis carried out (Chapter 5. Problem analysis) showed a set of problems in the region, both in terms of conservation and development and organization that conspire with the achievement of the goals of the initiative. To face this situation, three fundamental strategies are proposed: The maintenance or restoration of the connectivity and integrity of ecosystems and populations of priority species, the promotion of the valuation and sustainable use of biodiversity, and the assurance of financial sufficiency and strengthening governance for conservation management. The Plan's theory of change (Figure 7) assumes that implementing truly transformative measures means that:

- a) Innovative tools and solutions are introduced to address development problems, and towards climate change adaptation, which place biodiversity in the center of attention with an inclusive and participatory approach.
- b) Measures are supported with adequate conditions and means of implementation, including financial resources, capacity, and technology.
- c) Threats to biological diversity are effectively and significantly reduced.
- d) It ensures that biological diversity is used sustainably to meet the needs of people.
- e) Progress is transparently and accountably tracked, with appropriate stocktaking exercises, to ensure that by 2030 the CBC is on track to achieve its 2050 Vision.

One hundred activities have been identified (See section 6.2 Program of activities). Eighteen outputs are expected that would allow six outcomes responding to the three strategic goals defined by the intervention strategies. The following section describes the outputs and outcomes for each of the goals, which should lead to the achievement of the medium- and long-term impacts declared in the theory of change.

6.2.1 Strategic intervention goals, outcomes, and outputs

Goal 1: The integrity and connectivity of all priority ecosystems is improved

The expected results under this objective are aligned with the strategic axes of ensuring conservation, maintaining connectivity, and strengthening resilience to climate change. To achieve this, five outputs must be worked on: The increase and consolidation of the CBC conservation system, the restoration of degraded ecosystems, the strengthening of resilience to climate change, the effective protection of priority species and the reduction of environmental pollution. Central aspects of this goal are, therefore, the achievement of the effective conservation of the most representative, best connected, and most resilient values of the ecosystems and wild species of the Caribbean islands integrated into the initiative, the maintenance of the capacity of ecosystems to provide key environmental services, as well as the restoration of connectivity between the remaining patches of well-preserved and adequately protected natural spaces. This is also intended to make a significant contribution to ecosystem-based climate change adaptation strategies by reducing non-climate threats.

The continuous development of the initiative incorporating new territories of importance for regional connectivity, as well as increasing the coverage of areas that ensure the effective conservation of biodiversity and the representativeness of all priority ecosystems, including terrestrial and marine protected areas (PA) or other effective area-based conservation measures (OECM), is one of the outputs of the Plan that must be ensured. For this, it will not be enough to increase the coverage of protected areas with emphasis on marine areas where the main gaps persist, but other spatially explicit conservation instruments will be necessary. It will require the adoption of comprehensive approaches that reconcile the processes of conservation, restoration, and production at the landscape scale. Land and seascapes are required to be the object of spatial, multisectoral and integrated planning that contributes to the conservation of biodiversity and its connectivity, beyond traditional pathways based exclusively on protected areas. It will be necessary to strengthen the processes of participatory territorial planning in the CBC, integrating conservation figures into them to ensure their formal recognition and social legitimacy.

These processes should consider not only protected areas, but also ecological corridors, connectivity conservation areas; areas of special interest for nature tourism; areas of high conservation value; buffer zones; areas of sustainable fishing, agroecological or agroforestry systems; hydro-regulating natural forest strips, protective forests with effective management and protected water sources; suburban or urban recreational forest parks; and/or other effective conservation measures at the site and landscape level. In the process of integrating conservation into land use planning, coordination and harmonization of environmental institutions and policies with those of other sectors (agriculture, fishing, tourism, infrastructure, hydrocarbons, mining, and other relevant sectors) must be guaranteed.

On the other hand, the CBC must promote spatial planning with an ecosystem approach and at ecologically appropriate scales, considering harmonization at

15 PROGRAMS WITH 100 ACTIVITIES

Current situations

- Loss of habitat and connectivity
- Overfishing, bycatch and impact of fishing gear
- Illegal hunting, capture or collection
- Introduced, invasives and/or predatory species
- Infrastructure, urbanization and pollution
- Climate change
- Insufficient protection

- Lack of financial sustainability
- Insufficient formal arrangements with key actors
- Limited intervention at the local scale
- Weak incorporation of the marine theme
- Insufficient technical capacity
- Insufficient ICT infrastructure
- Political instability and changes
- Geographical extension and fragmentation of the Caribbean

all territorial levels (local, national, and regional/transboundary). The CBC must continue working to consolidate its role in environmental integration among the different countries that adhere to the initiative, prioritizing concerted action and management of shared ecosystems and biodiversity resources, such as some transboundary hydrographic basins (in the case of Hispaniola), cross-border fishing areas or ecologically interconnected fishing or tourism resources, such as reefs and mangroves, as well as many species of economic or conservation importance associated with them (fish, sea turtles, marine mammals).

The expected outcomes and outputs under this goal are as follows:

OUTCOME 1.1: The geographic scope of the CBC is expanded, the integrity and connectivity of terrestrial and marine ecosystems is improved, and wild species (threatened, endemic, and migratory), their genetic diversity, and key habitats are effectively protected and conserved, considering climate change, and ensuring the provision of ecosystem goods and services.

- **Output 1.1.1:** The spatial scope of the CBC is expanded to fill conservation gaps and incorporate new territories, and it is guaranteed that at least 30% of its demarcation are effectively conserved through protected areas (PAs) systems, and other effective area-based conservation measures (OECM)⁹, managed in an integrated and sustainable¹⁰ manner.
- **Output 1.1.2:** Populations of CBC priority species and their genetic diversity are protected, recovered, and conserved, and human-wildlife interactions are effectively managed¹¹ considering conditions of a changing climate.
- **Output 1.1.3:** Connectivity and ecological integrity of terrestrial, coastal and marine landscapes are improved, and at least 20% of degraded watersheds; inland waters, wetlands, , marine, coastal and terrestrial ecosystems in CBC priority areas for restoration are under restoration to ensure regional connectivity, considering conditions posed by a changing climate.
- **Output 1.1.4:** The current and potential impacts of climate change on biodiversity are assessed and reduced to the minimum feasible through nature-based solutions and EbA measures¹².
- **Output 1.1.5:** Pollution is reduced to levels that are not harmful to biodiversity, ecosystem functions, and human health in at least 50% of the most important sources selected by the countries¹³.

OUTCOME 1.2: Territorial development of key landscapes and seascapes of the CBC is planned with a spatial, holistic, and cooperative approach.

- **Output 1.2.1:** Coastal marine and Terrestrial Key areas for the CBC are under a multisectoral, participative and integrated land use planning scheme that considers biodiversity¹⁴.

⁹Ecologically representative, well connected and resilient to climate change.

¹⁰Prioritizing those of particular importance for biological diversity and its contributions to people.

¹¹To avoid or reduce conflicts, ensuring that the collection, use, and wildlife trade are sustainable, legal, and safe for human and ecosystem health.

¹²Contributing to improve and ensure both the resilience of communities and the contributions to national mitigation goals.

¹³Considering its impacts over CBC Priorities.

¹⁴In response to changes in use, guaranteeing the effective protection of remaining wild areas and promoting landscape-level restoration of degraded ecosystems.

Goal 2: The contributions of terrestrial and marine ecosystem goods and services are valued and maintained or enhanced through sustainable use of resources, and support the development agenda to benefit all, particularly most vulnerable communities.

It is necessary to achieve a significant increase in local actions to mitigate threats to priority biodiversity through the promotion of truly sustainable local development in harmony with nature. To do this, the first step must be to develop detailed conservation problem analysis in priority territories that allow collecting the necessary information on the problem to be faced, following the guidelines defined and approved for the development of projects. The activities must contribute to the effective management and sustainable use of wild species, protecting their customary use by local communities, and ensuring economic benefits, food security, traditional medicines, and livelihoods for people, especially the most vulnerable. This requires working on multisectoral planning and local development policies as well as on the generation of sustainable alternatives for local communities, with a gender approach that allows for the integration, autonomy, and empowerment of women and other vulnerable groups.

An important aspect is to guarantee that the incentives (economic, regulatory, public, and private) that are implemented in the territories favor, or at least do not harm, the conservation and restoration of biodiversity and its connectivity in the scope of the CBC. Also central is the need to raise awareness and understanding of human-wildlife interactions, the social and environmental impacts of unsustainable use of natural resources, and the benefits of alternative livelihoods for communities. For this, a communication strategy must be developed to support conservation and the reduction of threats on the CBC conservation priorities.

The need for a broader and better focused communication about the CBC, its results, and benefits, was identified as a weakness. A strategic line in this aspect will focus on developing, updating, and implementing a social communication plan that is fundamentally based on the use of social networks and local mass media (such as radio and television). The communication strategy must also implement effective mechanisms to maintain the flow of information and news from the main partners of the CBC in each of the countries for its effective dissemination through the CBC media. Additionally, it is necessary to strengthen the technical capacities of different actors so that they can implement the actions and sustainable alternatives that are identified.

To achieve this goal, it is also required that nature and its contributions to the economy and life of communities be properly valued and accounted for, and that the data from these valuations inform decisions, an aspect on which there is little experience. Even at the CBC. The fair and holistic valuation of nature and its contributions to the economy and to the means and quality of life of communities and territories should also serve as a basis to help establish financial mechanisms that allow the economic sustainability of conservation. This last aspect will be taken up again in Goal 3.

The expected outcomes and outputs under this goal are as follows:

OUTCOME 2.1: Long-term sustainability of nature-based livelihoods and enterprises is ensured¹⁵.

- **Output 2.1.1:** Incentives and tools that promote the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity are incorporated and sustainable¹⁶ practices and livelihoods¹⁷ are promoted and implemented in at least 50% of the priority agricultural, fishing and forestry areas for the CBC¹⁸.
- **Output 2.1.2:** Awareness and understanding of human-wildlife interactions, the social and environmental impacts of unsustainable use of natural resources, and the benefits of alternative livelihoods at local, national, and regional scales are strengthened.

OUTCOME 2.2: Contributions of terrestrial, coastal and marine ecosystem goods and services are accounted for to support decision-making.

- **Output 2.2.1:** National contributions to conservation in the CBC, and the value of ecosystem services are accounted for; and the alignment of financial instruments and flows with the values of biodiversity is measured.

Goal 3: The gap between the necessary and available knowledge and resources¹⁹ is closed, and the conditions to achieve the 2050 Vision are ensured.

To achieve financial sustainability, it is necessary to ensure the development of one or more patrimonial funds of the CBC, establish strategic alliances, develop a plan to search for funds, and follow up on the Financial Strategy Implementation Plan. Work should also be done on at least two “umbrella” projects, one for the terrestrial sphere and the other for the marine-coastal sphere, but which are integrated and complemented in an approach from the top to the reefs (Ridge-to-Reef), since that since the health of the oceans also depends on the proper management of ecosystems and biodiversity in the terrestrial zone. In addition, other actions that contribute to the priorities of the CBC should be promoted through coordinated projects or independent projects executed by key partners of the CBC who want to contribute and recognize their contribution to the initiative. It is required that the necessary financial resources to implement the Strategic Action Plan of the CBC are available and implemented, progressively closing the financing gap for actions of a regional nature and to support member countries until reaching at least US\$1,500,000 per year by 2030 and ensuring resources for the period 2032 to 2042.

¹⁵With emphasis on the responsible and sustainable use of shared biotic resources by more than one country, with clear contribution to relevant SDGs.

¹⁶It includes, among other measures, the creation of value chains and certifications of sustainability and/or environmental responsibility.

¹⁷With support of local communities and stakeholders, sustainable use and management of wildlife is ensured, as well as the connectivity of ecosystems at regional scale, productivity is improved and contributes to increase climate

change resilience of terrestrial and marine landscapes under productive socioeconomic uses.

¹⁸Priority areas for agriculture, fishing and forestry in the CBC will be selected in each country based on their importance for biodiversity conservation and considering each country's capacity and feasibility to implement sustainability practices and incentives.

¹⁹Financial, technical and organizational; as well as on capacities and other means of implementation.

On the other hand, it is necessary to continue strengthening the development of the CBC as an institution and its governance system. In order to strengthen the Secretariat, it is necessary to reinforce it with trained, young and fluent personnel and achieve the formalization of its legal status. This process must be achieved while maintaining high professional quality, experience, dedication, and representativeness by country; while safeguarding the perception that the Secretariat is a decentralized entity with enough independence to carry out its work, but at the same time it does so for the ministries of the environment and for the priorities of the countries.

Related to institutional strengthening and development, the need to establish formal agreements with key actors and coordinated projects is also identified so that synergies can be taken advantage of, establishing transparent working and cooperation relationships; the need to improve the technological communication infrastructure for remote joint work, which in times of COVID-19 has proven to be possible and useful, but still presents technological and financing challenges.

An essential part of strengthening the CBC governance and institutionality is the continuous development of the Integrated Knowledge Management System (IKMS) and all the support system and tools that it requires. The aim is to turn the IKMS into a useful instrument that systematically produces relevant, updated, and timely information to support informed decision-making. Work should also be done to strengthen the mechanisms to monitor, evaluate and advise the implementation of activities in the field and the progress of the initiative. In this context, to promote the effectiveness and strengthen the success and adaptability of biodiversity management in favor of sustainable development within the framework of the CBC, a robust, updated, and relevant knowledge base is required. The information must be compiled and presented in a way that allows:

- a) Define and structure the problems to be faced.
- b) Design attainable goals.
- c) Identify and evaluate the barriers to overcome to achieve the goals.
- d) Identify and evaluate possible alternatives to overcome barriers and achieve goals.
- e) Make decisions about alternative courses of action to follow.
- f) Measure the success of conservation and development management.
- g) Modify management accordingly.

The knowledge and information necessary for these processes are produced in two fundamental ways: cooperative monitoring of regionally important biodiversity and management effectiveness, and joint biodiversity research in a South-South cooperation framework.

On the other hand, for the CBC it is important to provide training in the topics that are determined as priorities for the ministries and to support the postgraduate training of key people, taking advantage of the opportunities to create alliances and postgraduate training plans with academic institutions. The implementation of actions on the ground also requires training to disseminate new knowledge and encourage new practices. ICTs today allow the development of online teaching-learning platforms that allow the impact of training to be extended, although in rural conditions face-to-face meetings will continue to be a fundamental tool. During

the organization of the collection of monitoring information, and in the training to implement activities in the field, a gender approach will be applied to ensure the integration and empowerment of women and other vulnerable groups from the communities surrounding the sites where they are going. to implement the actions.

Continuous updating and improvement of the initiative's web page must be maintained, as a portal to access the tools of the Integrated Knowledge Management System and to disseminate its tools, potential and benefits among potential users. The expected outcomes and outputs under this goal are as follows:

OUTCOME 3.1: The financial resources necessary to implement the CBC Strategic Plan are available and implemented.

- **Output 3.1.1:** It is ensured that the financial resources of regional scope necessary to achieve the objectives and goals of the initiative in the short, medium, and long-term are gradually increased²⁰.

OUTCOME 3.2: Strengthened capacity of the CBC as a governance mechanism and South-South cooperation platform for capacity building, knowledge generation, and facilitating access to relevant information for decision-making for the benefit of national and local governments, and communities, and to implement the CBC Strategic Plan in both the marine and terrestrial realm.

- **Output 3.2.1:** Relevant best knowledge, including traditional knowledge, is compiled, or generated, made accessible and guides decision-making for the effective management of biological diversity in the CBC and beyond²¹.
- **Output 3.2.2:** It is ensured that legislation, policies, regulations, territorial plans, development processes and poverty reduction strategies explicitly consider and favor the conservation and restoration of biological diversity values, in all relevant sectors in the spatial scope of the CBC.
- **Output 3.2.3:** The capacities of key actors for productive and ecological restoration of terrestrial and marine ecosystems are strengthened; EbA, planning and integrated management of the sustainable use of natural resources; and to assess the socio-ecological impacts of restoration and conservation initiatives.
- **Output 3.2.4:** The capacity of the Executive Secretariat of the CBC and of the initiative in general is strengthened and renewed.

²⁰It includes both project funds and endowment funds, guaranteeing the diversification of the CBC's financial sources and stimulating the growth of national investments in conservation.

²¹Helping improve cooperation for conservation in the regions connected to the Corridor.

6.2 PROGRAM OF ACTIVITIES

The proposed 100 activities to achieve the outputs, outcomes and goals are presented here grouped into 15 work programs with a tentative schedule for implementation.

Nº	ACTIVITIES	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
GOAL 1: THE INTEGRITY AND CONNECTIVITY OF ALL PRIORITY ECOSYSTEMS IS IMPROVED										
Outcome 1.1: The geographic scope of the CBC is expanded, the integrity and connectivity of terrestrial and marine ecosystems is improved, and wild species (threatened, endemic, and migratory), their genetic diversity, and key habitats are effectively protected and conserved, considering climate change, and ensuring the provision of ecosystem goods and services.										
Output 1.1.1: The spatial scope of the CBC is expanded to fill conservation gaps and incorporate new territories, and it is guaranteed that at least 30% of the terrestrial and marine areas of its demarcation are effectively conserved through ecologically representative, well-connected systems and resilient to climate change of protected areas (PAs) systems, ecologically and biologically sensitive areas (EBSAs), and other effective area-based conservation measures (OECM), managed in an integrated and sustainable.										
1. Conservation management planning and improvement program										
1	Analysis and development of agreed evaluation standards of the existing and potential spectrum of areas that can be considered as OECM									
2	Analysis and prioritization of conservation gaps on a regional scale that consider not only representativeness, but also connectivity and resilience to climate change, and identify new priority areas for conservation (Possible expansions, or new PAs or OECM).									
3	Implementation of modifications to PAs and/or creation of new PAs or OECM, to reach at least 30% under effective conservation through systems of ecologically representative areas, well connected and resilient to climate change.									
4	Reanalysis and update of the conservation priorities of the CBC developing new criteria in alignment with the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework, and other relevant guidelines									
5	Analysis of the effectiveness of the PA and OECM for the conservation of the priorities of the CBC in key areas, and proposals for measures for their improvement.									
6	Support for the strengthening of financial and technical capacities for the effective management of priority core areas for the CBC.									
7	Support for the introduction and implementation processes of agreed standards for PA and OECM management within the framework of the initiative, as well as other international designations or certifications, such as the IUCN Green List, Blue Parks, and other international designations or certifications or those agreed within the framework of the initiative.									
8	Support for the formulation of robust management plans in key areas (PA or OECM) for the CBC, ensuring that they are effective and consider the regional dimension.									

Nº	ACTIVITIES	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
9	Support for the development and implementation of robust national conservation plans (National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans, Protected Area System Plans or any other) that harmonize with the regional conservation goals agreed upon for the CBC.									
10	Evaluate, identify and facilitate the incorporation of new countries or territories to the initiative, considering their potential contribution to regional connectivity and to the extent that interests arise for other states to join the initiative.									
Output 1.1.2: Populations of CBC priority species and their genetic diversity are protected, restored and conserved, and human-wildlife interactions are effectively managed considering conditions of a changing climate.										
2. Species conservation program										
11	Support for the formulation and implementation of conservation and threat mitigation plans for terrestrial and marine priority species.									
12	Promotion and support for the implementation of prevention measures, threat control and rapid response systems to processes that affect terrestrial and marine species and ecosystems and that impact communities, such as forest fires, algae blooms and sargassum arrival and any other considered high priority.									
13	Promotion and implementation of policies, plans and programmes for the protection, reintroduction, and enrichment of ecosystems with threatened or priority species, and native species of high value for communities.									
14	Periodic evaluation of the incidence and impact of invasive alien species on ecosystems and priority species of the CBC considering possible interactions of such threats with other actions contemplated in the Strategic Plan.									
15	Support for the formulation and implementation of plans for the control or elimination of invasive alien species in key areas of the CBC, prioritizing the cases with greater impact or related to other actions of the Strategic Plan.									
16	Promotion and consensual formulation of a Subregional Action Plan for the Conservation of Biodiversity, as support for the fulfillment of the commitments with the CBD.									
Output 1.1.3: Connectivity and ecological integrity of terrestrial, coastal and marine landscapes are improved, and at least 20% of degraded watersheds; inland waters, wetlands, freshwater, marine, coastal and terrestrial ecosystems in CBC priority areas for restoration are under restoration to ensure regional connectivity, considering conditions posed by a changing climate.										
3. Connectivity Restoration Program										
17	Identification of terrestrial, coastal and marine priority areas for restoration in the CBC.									
18	Identification of the most convenient and feasible restoration pathways and methods for each selected site, and ecosystem considering the feasibility of involving local communities and a gender-sensitive approach, in the context of a changing climate.									

Nº	ACTIVITIES	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
19	Support for the implementation and development of actions to restore key terrestrial coastal and marine landscapes, ecosystems, and habitats with community participation, a cross-cutting gender-sensitive approach ensuring their effectiveness in the context of a changing climate.									
20	Evaluation of the success of the restoration.									
Output 1.1.4: The current and potential impacts of climate change on biodiversity are assessed and reduced to the minimum feasible through nature-based solutions and EbA measures										
4. Climate change adaptation and mitigation program										
21	Carry out intersectional and participatory diagnoses with a gender sensitive approach and climate change vulnerability analysis both for the areas, ecosystems, priority species of the CBC, as well as for the human communities linked to said areas and ecosystems.									
22	Introduce the climate change dimension in PA and OECM planning.									
23	Mainstream EbA measures and other nature-based solutions to address climate change and improve the sustainability of the use of natural resources with gender-sensitive participation of local communities.									
24	Promote and implement measures that contribute to mitigation and carbon sequestration as a contribution to the nationally determined contributions (NDC) both in terrestrial ecosystems as well as in coastal and marine.									
Output 1.1.5: Pollution is reduced to levels that are not harmful to biodiversity, ecosystem functions, and human health in at least 50% of the most important sources selected by the countries										
5. Pollution impact reduction program										
25	Develop and implement studies to evaluate the impacts of pollution on biodiversity, and for the prioritization of key areas for combating pollution within the framework of the CBC.									
26	Promote and support the implementation of pollution prevention and control initiatives and systems, including separate collection, reuse, recycling, treatment and use of residues and waste (organic and inorganic of various origins, with an emphasis on plastics), with a circular economy approach in communities of priority sites for the CBC, with special emphasis on the tourism, commercial, fishing and agricultural sectors.									
27	Promotion of the use of biodegradable organic fertilizers and pesticides, biological control systems for pests and diseases, and good agroecological and forestry practices to reduce pollution caused by agricultural chemicals									
Outcome 1.2 Territorial development of key landscapes and seascapes of the CBC is planned with a spatial, holistic, and cooperative approach.										
Output 1.2.1: Coastal marine and Terrestrial Key areas for the CBC are under a multisectoral, participative and integrated land use planning scheme that considers biodiversity.										
6. Program for the development of integrated territorial planning										

Nº	ACTIVITIES	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
28	Support for the formation of new consensual visions about territorial development in national and local governments, which promote sustainability with a cross-sectoral, integrated and circular economy approach.									
29	Development of a dissemination and awareness plan about the CBC in the institutions in charge of planning and managing biodiversity resources in the member countries of the initiative, to incorporate the demarcation and priorities of the CBC in their development plans and of territorial planning.									
30	Promote spatial planning plans at the landscape level (terrestrial or marine) with an integrated approach, that explicitly incorporate relevant conservation figures, such as protected areas and OECM, and that promote environmental sustainability with a participatory, cross-sectoral and circular economy approach.									
31	Develop analyzes and identify recommendations to improve national contributions to the sustainability of regional development and conservation.									
GOAL 2: THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF TERRESTRIAL AND MARINE ECOSYSTEM GOODS AND SERVICES ARE VALUED AND MAINTAINED OR ENHANCED THROUGH SUSTAINABLE USE OF RESOURCES, AND SUPPORT THE DEVELOPMENT AGENDA WHO BENEFIT ALL, PARTICULARLY MOST VULNERABLE COMMUNITIES.										
Outcome 2.1: Long-term sustainability of nature-based livelihoods and enterprises is ensured										
Output 2.1.1: Incentives and tools that promote the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity are incorporated and sustainable practices and livelihoods are promoted and implemented in at least 50% of the priority agricultural, fishing and forestry areas for the CBC.										
7. Program to promote sustainable development in local communities										
32	Identification, hierarchy and prioritization of existing economic, social or policy incentives that drive unsustainable practices or affect biodiversity, contribute to climate change, and generate pollution and the prioritization of actions that reduce or eliminate them.									
33	Identification of potentialities for the creation of incentives for sustainability at the national and local levels, with a participatory and gender-sensitive approach.									
34	Develop and implement an action plan to combat perverse incentives for biodiversity and the environment and in place stimulate positive or neutral incentives.									
35	Support to countries in the implementation of specific measures to transform negative incentives for biodiversity into neutral or positive incentives.									
36	Support to countries, local governments, and communities in the creation of incentives for sustainable practices and the promotion of certification systems, brands and appellations of origin that contribute to the creation of fair markets for locally produced sustainable products.									

Nº	ACTIVITIES	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
37	Promotion and support for the implementation of fair financial mechanisms that promote innovation and the development of sustainable practices in the local communities of the CBC.									
38	Development, by the partners of the CBC in the countries, of territorial diagnoses (with information disaggregated by gender, age groups and social groups, etc.) that allow prioritizing vulnerable areas, communities, and groups for the implementation of conservation projects, EbA, and local sustainable development in the CBC.									
39	Study of productive practices and livelihoods in key communities of the CBC and participatory identification of possible alternatives for sustainable livelihoods.									
40	Promotion and support for the study of possible production chains and value chains, and identification of new fair markets for sustainable local production as a way to improve livelihoods and reduce pressure on biodiversity in key sites for the CBC.									
41	Promotion of the implementation of livelihoods and sustainable production practices, and promotion of sustainable products, offering new job opportunities for youth and disadvantaged groups in key local communities of the CBC.									
42	Promotion of environmentally friendly, alternative domestic fuels and more efficient domestic energy systems with a lower carbon footprint.									
43	Promote sustainable consumption and production patterns that contribute to reducing the ecological footprint of human communities.									
Outcome 2.1.2: Awareness and understanding of human-wildlife interactions, the social and environmental impacts of unsustainable use of natural resources, and the benefits of alternative livelihoods at local, national, and regional scales are strengthened.										
8. Social communication program for conservation and sustainable development										
44	Develop, up-to-date maintenance, and monitoring of the implementation of a social communication plan that is fundamentally based on the use of social networks and local mass media (radio and TV) and contributes to raising general awareness about the CBC, its values, priorities, achievements, importance and benefits.									
45	Develop and implement a communication and awareness campaign to the following topics: a) Support the conservation and mitigation of threats to priority species for the CBC, in close relationship with the actions of the corresponding conservation programs. b) Improve understanding of human-wildlife interactions. c) Promote sustainable livelihood alternatives in rural communities in priority areas of the CBC. d) Stimulate the conservation of forests, mangroves and reefs and reforestation in degraded areas and protection strips of rivers and coasts.									

Nº	ACTIVITIES	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
44	e) Support the implementation of nature-based solutions to adapt to climate change. f) Improve general environmental education and awareness of key actors in local communities. g) Stimulate the reduction of the use of single-use plastics and other pollutants, as well as the proper use and management of organic and inorganic waste with a circular economy approach.									
Outcome 2.2: Contributions of terrestrial, coastal and marine ecosystem goods and services are accounted for to support decision-making.										
Output 2.2.1: Accounting for national contributions to conservation in the CBC, and the value of ecosystem services are accounted for; as well as measurement of the alignment of financial instruments and flows with the values of biodiversity is measured.										
9. Valuation program of contributions to the CBC and of nature's contributions to economies										
46	Establishment of a system for accounting for the contributions of the member countries to the implementation of the Strategic Action Plan of the CBC.									
47	Identification or development, and promotion of adequate tools for valuing the contributions of ecosystems to local economies, communities, and businesses.									
48	Evaluation of the current state of knowledge about the contributions of biodiversity and its economic value, as well as its application in decision-making in key areas for the CBC.									
49	Valuation studies of ecosystem services in priority areas for the CBC.									
50	Promotion and support for the evaluation of the contributions of ecosystems to the economies of communities, companies, and territories in the CBC.									
51	Analysis and proposal to the countries of a set of recommendations to ensure that environmental impact assessments and productive activities in key areas of the CBC consider and align with the values of biodiversity, and with the climate resilience of the most vulnerable communities.									
52	Systematic assessment of the extent to which financial flows in key areas of the initiative are aligned with and consider biodiversity values.									
GOAL 3: THE GAP BETWEEN THE NECESSARY AND AVAILABLE RESOURCES IS CLOSED AND CONDITIONS ARE ENSURED TO ACHIEVE THE VISION BY 2050										
Outcome 3.1: The financial resources necessary to implement the CBC Strategic Action Plan are available and implemented.										
Output 3.1.1: It is ensured that the financial resources of regional scope necessary to achieve the objectives and goals of the initiative are gradually increased.										
10. Financial sustainability program										
53	Completion of the working mechanisms of the CBC-CBF-UNEP and CBC-UNEP strategic alliances for the development of the CBC Endowment Funds, ensure the financial sustainability of the initiative's governance system and, in the long term, support actions on the ground.									

Nº	ACTIVITIES	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
54	Completion and development of the legal and regulatory framework and the working mechanisms for the use of the resources generated by the Endowment Funds of the CBC									
55	Development of appropriate CBC informational materials to support fundraising.									
56	Development of donor tables aimed at seeking support for CBC patrimonial funds.									
57	Preparation of a pool of potential donors from the private sector who can sponsor CBC programs or contribute to the endowment funds.									
58	Systematic updating of the work plan to secure the necessary financial resources for the CBC's endowment funds to guarantee the self-sufficient functioning of the governance platform, the maintenance of the services it provides and the implementation of priority actions on the ground in the long term.									
59	Systematic monitoring of financing opportunities according to the topics that are supported, models/types of financing, dates of calls, and articulation, synergies and lobbying that they require.									
60	Maintain an updated portfolio of concept notes and projects that allow the implementation of the Strategic Action Plan of the CBC.									
61	Support to key partners in the identification of opportunities and the preparation of coordinated or independent projects that contribute to the implementation of the Strategic Action Plan.									
62	Promotion, monitoring, and support for coordinated projects that support the implementation of actions at the local level that contribute to the conservation priorities of the CBC and to improve the sustainability of the livelihoods of the communities in the territory.									
63	Assurance of funds to implement large projects (both for land and marine-coastal) that allow the implementation of the Strategic Action Plan.									
64	Explore diverse financing pathways for the CBC, such as crowdfunding, sale of souvenirs, contributions for the support of the management of coordinated projects, among other.									
65	Promote new financial mechanisms in the countries of the CBC initiative to support its objectives, such as: environmental taxes and fees, payment for ecosystem services, contributions from the private sector to complement public sources (donations and/or loans), inclusion of budget lines aimed at avoiding, minimizing, restoring and compensating the socio-environmental impacts of development programs and projects; promoting the development of markets for products certified as green or sustainable and develop and implement debt-for nature swaps or debt-for-climate swaps, according to the countries' will and opportunities for it.									

Nº	ACTIVITIES	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
66	Systematic review, updating and approval of the CBC financial plan/strategy.									
67	Preparation of a new version of the financial strategy to ensure the necessary financial, technical, and human resources for the period 2032 to 2042.									
<p>Outcome 3.2: Strengthened capacity of the CBC as a governance mechanism and South-South cooperation platform for capacity building, knowledge generation, and facilitating access to relevant information for decision-making for the benefit of national and local governments, and communities, and to implement the CBC Action Strategic Plan in both the marine and terrestrial realm.</p>										
<p>Output 3.2.1: Relevant best knowledge, including traditional knowledge, is compiled, or generated, made accessible and guides decision-making for the effective management of biological diversity in the CBC and beyond</p>										
11. Program to strengthen knowledge management and associated services										
68	Expansion of the capabilities, tools, and services of the CBC's Integrated Knowledge Management System so that it is more effective in supporting decision-making, providing the best and most relevant information available, prioritizing the relative future climate projections and the development of information -exchange mechanisms on protected areas and OECM.									
69	Maintenance and expansion of the technological capabilities of the platform that supports the Integrated Knowledge Management System, as required based on the demand for information and the development of the tools to be implemented.									
70	Continuous updation and improvement of the CBC BioAtlas tool to include new data, analysis, and reporting tools to meet information needs to support CBC decision-making and project management, prioritizing climate change future projections relevant data..									
71	Identification, adoption and/or development and application of tools for collecting in the field, transmission and systematization of data and information to support monitoring, both by specialists and technicians, as well as by the population interested in citizen science.									
72	Systematic update of the scientific-technical documentation relevant to the CBC that is available to the public through its information portal and continuous improvement of the tools for searching and exchanging information.									
73	Constant maintenance, updating and development of the CBC website as a portal to access relevant information.									
12. Monitoring and Research Program										
74	Maintenance and strengthening of the regional system for monitoring biodiversity and its threats, promoting the adoption of standardized monitoring protocols and the support and continuous development of monitoring in the field, by technological means or direct observation, both by scientific-technical personnel and by trained citizens, with emphasis on:									

Nº	ACTIVITIES	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
74	<p>a) The impact of the CC on the ecosystems and priority species of the CBC, and on the human communities within the demarcation of the CBC.</p> <p>b) The state of health and threats not associated with the climate that affect the priority species and ecosystems for the CBC.</p> <p>c) Connectivity processes, especially migrations.</p> <p>d) The effectiveness of conservation, restoration, and local development actions on the health of priority species and ecosystems of the CBC, and on the climate resilience of human communities within its demarcation.</p>									
75	Strengthening or development of early warning systems for the application of measures to prevent and combat forest fires, sargassum invasions, the spread of diseases, and other threats to ecosystems and wild species.									
76	<p>Promotion and development of biological inventories and rapid ecological assessments (IBR) and other studies that fill important knowledge gaps for the objectives of the initiative; including, but not limited to:</p> <p>a) Studies to complete the knowledge of biodiversity in core areas of the CBC.</p> <p>b) Biodiversity studies in key sites for the improvement of connectivity and the implementation of ecological corridors.</p> <p>c) Biodiversity studies of deep-sea ecosystems.</p> <p>d) Improvement of the inventory and mapping of the distribution of ecoregions, ecosystems, habitats and priority species.</p> <p>e) Improvement of knowledge about the processes and patterns of dispersion and migration of gametes and individuals of priority and migratory species important for regional connectivity.</p>									
<p>Output 3.2.2: It is ensured that legislation, policies, regulations, territorial plans, development processes and poverty reduction strategies explicitly consider and favor the conservation and restoration of biological diversity values, in all relevant sectors in the spatial scope of the CBC.</p>										
<p>13. Program to strengthen the legal framework and policies for conservation</p>										
77	Review, evaluation, identification of gaps and proposals for the reformulation of the legal instruments that support the implementation of the CBC, and ecological corridors in general and that stimulate the consideration of the values of biodiversity in territorial development.									
78	Review, evaluation, identification of gaps and proposals to improve socioeconomic development policies so they can help conserve or reduce the impacts on biodiversity and favor the conservation and restoration of ecosystems and to maintain the environmental services they provide.									

Nº	ACTIVITIES	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
79	Incorporation of the dimension of conservation and sustainable management of biodiversity resources in territorial planning policies and instruments, promoting an integrated approach that considers the analysis of threats to biodiversity, and recommendations to improve national contributions to biodiversity. sustainability of development and regional conservation.									
80	Support for the strengthening and implementation of forest policies and marine-coastal management in the CBC countries with a focus on conservation and sustainable use.									
Output 3.2.3: The capacities of key actors for productive and ecological restoration of terrestrial and marine ecosystems are strengthened; EbA, planning and integrated management of the sustainable use of natural resources; and to assess the socio-ecological impacts of restoration and conservation initiatives.										
14. Program to strengthen the scientific and technical capacity of key actors										
81	Systematic updating of the diagnosis of training and professional development needs of key CBC actors to seek opportunities									
82	Systematic development and updating of a professional training plan taking advantage of synergies and formal agreements with universities and other academic organizations (such as the Caribaea Initiative) as well as universities and research institutes in CBC countries.									
83	Systematic update and implementation of the portfolio of training courses on relevant topics for the implementation of projects in the field focused on the priorities of the CBC.									
84	Systematic update, growth, and maintenance of the set of trainings on topics relevant to the priorities of the CBC that are available online, and with free access, in the Virtual Teaching-Learning Environment of the CBC.									
85	Strengthening the capacity of key actors in priority issues, which include, but are not limited to: a) Sustainable forest governance, planning, management and its regulation. b) The planning, effective management and sustainable use of biodiversity, protected areas and other areas with effective conservation measures c) The identification and implementation of adaptation measures based on ecosystems d) The implementation of sustainable practices e) The implementation of integrated planning and management approaches, and adaptive management. f) Surveillance and law enforcement.									
86	Support the creation and development of a network of education institutions for capacity building on environmental management in the CBC.									
87	Support for the creation and development of a research and monitoring network within the framework of the CBC.									

Nº	ACTIVITIES	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Output 3.2.4: The capacity of the Executive Secretariat of the CBC and of the initiative in general is strengthened and renewed.										
15. Regional Governance Program										
88	Consolidation, approval, appropriation, and implementation of the Strategic Plan 2022-2030.									
89	Stable operation of the governance mechanism of the CBC, guaranteeing the effective and systematic celebration of Scientific-Technical and Ministerial Committees to follow up on the implementation of projects and the Strategic Action Plan.									
90	Facilitation and strengthening of exchanges of lessons learned and South-South cooperation to improve knowledge, the effectiveness of conservation, and promote the restoration and sustainable use of biodiversity.									
91	Strengthening of the capacity of the Secretariat to monitor, evaluate and advise the implementation of activities in the field and the progress of the initiative, both in actions developed by national partners and in its own projects.									
92	Inclusion of young, trained staff with language skills in the Secretariat, as required by the workload and filling current gaps in issues such as social communication and information technology, which have been solved with short-term consultancies.									
93	Develop together with UNEP the most appropriate and effective mechanism possible to legally formalize the Secretariat and the CBC initiative.									
94	Assurance of the working conditions and means of the Secretariat									
95	Establishment of new formal agreements, and systematic review of existing ones, with key actors for joint work, prioritizing those that carry out coordinated projects or independent projects that contribute to the priorities of the CBC.									
96	Establishment of new formal agreements, and systematic review of existing ones, with initiatives similar to the CBC.									
97	Promotion and implementation of actions, in coordination with the ministries of environment of the countries and territories of the CBC, to strengthen the capacities of the focal points so that they can improve the effectiveness in supporting the activities of the CBC, both in projects own, as coordinated or independent.									
98	Establishment of a platform with the necessary communication technology infrastructure for joint work and multilingual remote training of key actors in the countries participating in the initiative.									
99	Strengthening of the technical capacity in the Secretariat and the Ministries for the development and implementation of the social communication plans and campaigns of the CBC initiative and for the smooth updating of the CBC communication media.									
100	Review and update the Initiative ´s legal framework									

▶ Isla Cabritos, Lago Enriquillo, República Dominicana.

▲ Beekeeping and coffee bean harvesting, sustainable productivity activities in the Caribbean.

6.3 ESTIMATED BUDGET

An estimate of the minimum financial aspiration per management program is presented, with a total amount of USD 50.0 Million. This estimated budget is presented in detail by activity programs and each is linked to an output, outcome and goal.

Work is underway on a \$20 million eight-year project proposal focused only on the terrestrial level, with an emphasis on ecosystem-based restoration and adaptation. A second project of about USD 11 million would serve as a complement to promote conservation and sustainable development in the marine environment. Additionally, the fundraising of at least 19.0 million is expected to start supporting long-term financial sustainability through investment in endowment funds, so that the total budgeted for the Plan is reached.

The budget figures are only indicative and must be adjusted according to the real possibilities of collection. The degree of implementation that is achieved in the plan will depend on the levels of financing that are achieved through projects, the yields of the endowment funds, and the in-kind contributions of the member countries of the initiative through other plans and projects with budgets managed through national or local level. The broad and aligned participation with the plan carried out by government institutions, civil society and the private sector, and the accounting of their contributions, should be the fundamental source for the implementation of the Plan.

Table 6: Estimated budget (Thousands of USD)

Goal	Outcome	Output	Program	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	Total	
1	1.1	1.1.1	1. Conservation planning and management	50	100	200	200	200	100	100	100	100	1,150	
		1.1.2	2. Species Conservation	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	1,800
		1.1.3	3. Restoration of connectivity		500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	4,000
		1.1.4	4. Climate change	100	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	4,100
		1.1.5	5. Pollution reduction		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	50	750
	1.2	1.2.1	6. Integrated territorial planning		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	800
2	2.1	2.1.1	7. Sustainable development	100	600	800	800	800	800	800	800	800	800	6,300
		2.1.2	8. Social communication	75	200	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	975
	2.2	2.2.1	9. Valuation of contributions to the CBC and nature		95	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	795
3	3.1	3.1.1	10. Financial sustainability		1,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	2,500	19,000	
	3.2	3.2.1	11. Knowledge management and associated services	50	70	100	70	70	70	70	70	150	70	720
			12. Monitoring and Research	360	500	350	350	350	500	350			350	3,110
		3.2.2	13. Legal and policy framework	50	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	850
		3.2.3	14. Strengthening of technical capacities	100	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	2,500
		3.2.4	15. Regional governance	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	3,150
TOTAL				1,435	5,215	6,300	6,270	6,270	6,320	6,170	5,900	6,120	50,000	

6.4 MODEL FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ACTION PLAN

Figure 8 shows in a synthetic way the model of articulation of actions for the implementation of the Strategic Action Plan. A vertical articulation is proposed based on the commitments of the member countries of the initiative with the Multilateral Environmental Agreements (MEAs) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). They constitute the global framework that guides actions. Although the Plan is articulated with national priorities, it does not intend to supplant or duplicate national strategies; On the contrary, it seeks to fill gaps from a regional perspective and help countries reach consensus and coordinate actions to face and overcome common challenges.

The regional platform of the CBC should be securing funds not only to guarantee its operation at the regional level, but also to support the countries in the implementation of the actions of the plan. It will also work to promote the production and compilation of knowledge, and to provide tools and services to help countries generate information,

report their progress and support decision-making both at the regional level and in the member countries. CBC’s regional governance system will ensure that the results that are achieved are monitored and evaluated, that decisions are made by consensus and based on the best available information, and that a strategic alliance is maintained to define priorities and face common problems. The CBC’s South-South cooperation platform will also work on capacity building, providing training and scientific-technical support to governments and strategic partners in the member countries of the initiative. Finally, it will continue to provide social communication and education for the formation of environmental awareness. In its actions at the regional level, the CBC will seek support and synergies with other existing initiatives and networks in the region, avoiding duplication, multiplying positive impacts, and maximizing efficiency in the use of financial and human resources.

The implementation of the actions of the plan on the ground, however, is mostly carried out in and by the member countries of the initiative, with the participation not only of the ministries of the environment and their dependencies, but also with the support from numerous partners from academia, civil society, and the private sector. For this, the implementation will be based on the coordination, alignment, and synergy between different national and local projects with the activities identified in the plan. Actions will help countries conserve biodiversity and ensure sustainability, while achieving long-term visions for both the CBC and the world. ●

Figure 8: Model of articulation of the actions of the strategic plan of the CBC at the regional, global and national levels

► Coffee crops in agroforestry nursery in Pic Macayá, Haiti.

An aerial photograph of a rugged coastline. The left side shows dark, jagged rock formations with patches of green and brown vegetation. White waves are crashing against the rocks, creating foam. The rest of the image is dominated by deep blue, textured ocean water.

7

Summary of Environmental and Social Safeguards

7.1 SUMMARY OF ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL SAFEGUARDS

UNEP has designed a series of methodological tools for the identification of thematic and programmatic risks, which have been used to prepare this section of the plan. The evaluation of the safeguards resulted in a Moderate risk category for the Strategic Plan.

The Strategic Action Plan, being of moderate risk, must apply the “do no harm” principle to anticipate and prevent possible negative impacts in all CBC countries where interventions are to be carried out. Below is a set of recommendations that should be applied during the implementation of the Plan.

Regarding the standard of Safeguard 1: Biodiversity, Ecosystems and Sustainable Management of Natural Resources, the Plan will have a low risk, since it would not give rise to most of the potential risks related to this specific safeguard. On the contrary, its objective is to promote ecological and productive restoration in key ecosystems that comprise ecological corridors in the CBC countries.

With respect to Safeguard standard 2: Climate Change and Disaster Risk, the Plan will have a moderate risk. The project will anticipate and apply risk prevention, vulnerability reduction, resilience strengthening and good practices. In the Caribbean, recurrent disasters have greatly affected large sectors of the vulnerable population (not only because of poverty, but also because of the magnitude of the damage to infrastructure and the cost assigned for its recovery) and the region’s ecosystems.

Regarding the Safeguard 3 standard: pollution prevention and resource efficiency, the Plan will have a low risk since it has specific goals to reduce pollution, promote ecological restoration and sustainable livelihoods, trying to reduce pollution as much as possible. the amount of waste and the use of agrochemicals.

Regarding the standard of Safeguard 4: Health, Safety and Protection of the Community, the Plan will have a low risk. However, there will be some recommendations to better respond to endemic threats related to the specific ecosystems where the action takes place.

Regarding Safeguard standard 5: on Cultural Heritage, the Plan will have a low risk. Although the areas of intervention have not been determined exactly, a preliminary review concludes that there are some cultural heritage sites recognized by UNESCO, as well as other sites recognized by national and regional authorities. The authorities of the Plan will participate in a constructive dialogue for the coordination of the management plans. with the aim of collectively contributing to the protection and conservation of Cultural Heritage and Landscapes. The main objective will be to promote the harmonization of management plans for these sites, combining the possibility of improving natural and heritage protection.

Regarding Safeguard standard 6: Displacement and Involuntary Resettlement, the Plan will have a low risk, mainly linked to the possible possibility of restricting access to land in protected areas, where customary use has been granted. The project

aims to transform the traditional agricultural practices that the population has used for production and that are causing environmental damage. Sustainable livelihoods will be promoted. Through the application of conservation and restoration actions it is possible to restrict access to protected areas or the use of natural resources. However, the project action will promote sustainable livelihoods and access to sustainable value chains, the success of which will enhance ecosystem restoration and reduce pressure on key ecosystems.

With respect to Safeguard standard 7: On indigenous peoples, the risk is low because there are no self-identified indigenous populations in the intervention areas.

Regarding Safeguard standard 8: work and working conditions, it has been determined that the risk is low. The projects that will serve to implement the Plan will have execution personnel, field officers, and technical consultants. The implementation of the actions of these projects will consider the relevant occupational health and safety risks and the measures to prevent and mitigate their impacts. This includes the relevant biosecurity measures in the context of the pandemic, the application of the COVID protocols and their follow-up. The project will integrate the safety and health recommendations at work.

Finally, the Plan will ensure that a gender approach is incorporated and will promote gender-sensitive actions to prevent the reproduction and increase of inequality in this aspect. A gender action plan will be developed, providing a supporting bibliography for specific actions (recruitment, team building, publication, etc.). The results of this cross-cutting process will greatly enhance further gender integration in later phases of development of the CBC initiative. These considerations must also be aligned with international environmental and gender commitments, such as those arising from the COP (Lima work plan and COP 25 Gender Action Plan). ●

8

Annexes

Annex I: Synthesis of the conservation problem

Annex II: Factors that threaten the development of healthy, resilient and sustainable communities

Annex III: Results chain to achieve the effective conservation of CBC priorities and its connectivity

Annex IV: Results chain to achieve healthy, resilient and sustainable communities

Annex V: Logical Framework of the Strategic Plan

Goal 1: The integrity and connectivity of all priority ecosystems is improved				
Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ¹	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
1.1 The geographic scope of the CBC is expanded, the integrity and connectivity of marine and terrestrial ecosystems is improved, and wild species (threatened, endemic and migratory), their genetic diversity and key habitats are effectively protected and conserved, considering climate change and ensuring the provision of ecosystem goods and services.	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of new territories or countries incorporated into the CBC as of 2023</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> 2</p>	17.16.1 Number of countries reporting progress in multi-stakeholder development effectiveness monitoring frameworks that support the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals	<p>GOAL 1: Ensure that all areas are under participatory integrated biodiversity inclusive spatial planning and/or effective management processes addressing land and sea use change, to bring the loss of areas of high biodiversity importance, including ecosystems of high ecological integrity, close to zero by 2030, while respecting the rights of indigenous peoples and local communities.</p> <p>GOAL 20: Strengthen capacity-building and development, access to and transfer of technology, and promote development of and access to innovation and technical and scientific cooperation, including through South-South, North-South and triangular cooperation, to meet the needs for effective implementation, particularly in developing countries, fostering joint technology development and joint scientific research programmes for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity and strengthening scientific research and monitoring capacities, commensurate with the ambition of the goals and Goals of the framework.</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>i) Number of national or subnational entities that, with UNEP support, adopt integrated approaches to address environmental and social issues and/or tools for valuing, monitoring and sustainably managing biodiversity</p> <p>iii) Number of countries and national, regional and subnational authorities and entities that incorporate, with UNEP support, biodiversity and ecosystem-based approaches into development and sectoral plans, policies and processes for the sustainable management and/or restoration of terrestrial, freshwater and marine areas</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p> <p>Environmental Governance Subprogramme</p> <p>iv) Number of entities at the national, regional or global levels that UNEP has supported in developing integrated approaches and tools for enhanced coordination, cooperation and synergies for the coherent implementation of multilateral environmental agreements</p>
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of new protected areas or OECM incorporated or extended into the CBC as of 2023 that fill identified conservation gaps</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> 5</p>	<p>14.5.1 Coverage of protected areas in relation to marine areas</p> <p>15.1.2 Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by protected areas, by ecosystem type</p> <p>15.4.1 Coverage by protected areas of important sites for mountain biodiversity</p>	<p>GOAL 2: Ensure that by 2030 at least 30 per cent of areas of degraded terrestrial, inland water, and coastal and marine ecosystems are under effective restoration, in order to enhance biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services, ecological integrity and connectivity.</p> <p>GOAL 3: Ensure and enable that by 2030 at least 30 per cent of terrestrial, inland water, and of coastal and marine areas, especially areas of particular importance for biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services, are effectively conserved and managed through ecologically representative, well-connected and equitably governed systems of protected areas and other effective area-based conservation measures, recognizing indigenous and traditional territories, where applicable, and integrated into wider landscapes, seascapes and the ocean, while ensuring that any sustainable use, where appropriate in such areas, is fully consistent with conservation outcomes, recognizing and respecting the rights of indigenous peoples and local communities, including over their traditional territories.</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p>

¹ At time of writing, the Global Biodiversity Framework did not yet have specifically formulated Goals.

Goal 1: The integrity and connectivity of all priority ecosystems is improved				
Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ¹	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
Milestones showing progress towards achieving the outcome of the plan	Dates when milestones are expected			
There is an analysis of the territorial growth potential of the CBC	Dec-2024			
Incorporate a new territory	Dec-2027			
A second territory is incorporated	Dec-2030			
Key CBC PAs are selected, and their effectiveness assessed	Dec-2024			
The new demarcation of the CBC is reviewed, and the first group of new PAs is incorporated	Dec-2026			
A second group of PAs is incorporated	Dec-2030			
Periodic management effectiveness evaluations	At least every three years (2027 and 2030)			
Restoration plan ready for implementation	Dec-2024			
At least 50% of restoration plan successfully implemented	Dec-2028			
At least 90% of plan successfully implemented	Dec-2030			
Report on the status of populations of priority species with positive results	Dec-2030			
Outputs for Outcome 1.1				
1.1.1 The spatial scope of the CBC is expanded to fill conservation gaps and incorporate new territories, and it is guaranteed that at least 30% of the terrestrial and marine areas of its demarcation are effectively conserved through ecologically representative, well-connected systems and resilient to climate change of protected areas (PAs) systems, ecologically and biologically sensitive areas (EBSAs), and other effective area-based conservation measures (OECM), managed in an integrated and sustainable manner.	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Km2 of new territories or countries incorporated into the CBC from 2023</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> 20000</p>	17.16.1 Number of countries reporting progress in multi-stakeholder development effectiveness monitoring frameworks that support the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals	<p>GOAL 2:</p> <p>GOAL 3:</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iii) Number of countries and national, regional and subnational authorities and entities that incorporate, with UNEP support, biodiversity and ecosystem-based approaches into development and sectoral plans, policies and processes for the sustainable management and/or restoration of terrestrial, freshwater and marine areas</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p>

Goal 1: The integrity and connectivity of all priority ecosystems is improved				
Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ¹	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Km2 of new protected areas or ECMO incorporated or extended into the CBC from 2023 that fill identified conservation gaps</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0 <i>Target:</i> 800</p>	<p>14.5.1 Coverage of protected areas in relation to marine areas</p> <p>15.1.2 Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by protected areas, by ecosystem type</p> <p>15.4.1 Coverage by protected areas of important sites for mountain biodiversity</p>	<p>GOAL 2:</p> <p>GOAL 3:</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p>
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> % of key PAs increasing their effectiveness from 2023</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023 <i>Target:</i> 50%</p>	<p>15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management</p>	<p>GOAL 3:</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p>
<p>1.1.2 Populations of CBC priority species and their genetic diversity are protected, restored and conserved, and human-wildlife interactions are effectively managed considering conditions of a changing climate.</p>	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of priority species that at least maintain stable populations</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023 <i>Target:</i> At least doubles the number of priority species that maintain stable or growing populations</p>	<p>15.5.1 Red List Index</p> <p>15.7.1 Proportion of traded wildlife that was poached or illicitly trafficked</p> <p>15.c.1 Proportion of traded wildlife that was poached or illicitly trafficked</p>	<p>GOAL 4.</p> <p>GOAL 5: Ensure that the use, harvesting and trade of wild species is sustainable, safe and legal, preventing overexploitation, minimizing impacts on non-Goal species and ecosystems, and reducing the risk of pathogen spill-over, applying the ecosystem approach, while respecting and protecting customary sustainable use by indigenous peoples and local communities.</p> <p>GOAL 6: Eliminate, minimize, reduce and or mitigate the impacts of invasive alien species on biodiversity and ecosystem services by identifying and managing pathways of the introduction of alien species, preventing the introduction and establishment of priority invasive alien species, reducing the rates of introduction and establishment of other known or potential invasive alien species by at least 50 per cent, by 2030, eradicating or controlling invasive alien species especially in priority sites, such as islands.</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p>
<p>1.1.3 Connectivity and ecological integrity of terrestrial, coastal and marine landscapes are improved, and at least 20% of degraded watersheds: inland waters, wetlands, freshwater, marine, coastal and terrestrial ecosystems in CBC priority areas for restoration are under restoration to ensure regional connectivity, considering the conditions posed by a changing climate.</p>	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Km2 of degraded ecosystems under priority restoration that at least maintain stable populations</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023 <i>Target:</i> At least 20% of the areas prioritized for this activity in the CBC begin</p>	<p>14.2.1 Number of countries using ecosystem-based approaches to managing marine areas</p> <p>15.1.1 Forest area as a proportion of total land area</p> <p>15.3.1 Proportion of land that is degraded over total land area</p>	<p>GOAL 2</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p>

Goal 1: The integrity and connectivity of all priority ecosystems is improved				
Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ¹	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
1.1.4: Current and potential impacts of climate change on biodiversity are assessed and reduced to the minimum feasible	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of priority areas and/or communities with adaptation plans in implementation</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> In at least 70% of the key areas there are adaptation plans in implementation</p>	<p>13.1.2 Number of countries that adopt and implement national disaster risk reduction strategies in line with the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030</p> <p>13.1.3 Proportion of local governments that adopt and implement local disaster risk reduction strategies in line with national disaster risk reduction strategies</p> <p>13.2.1 Number of countries with nationally determined contributions, long-term strategies, national adaptation plans and adaptation communications, as reported to the secretariat of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change</p>	<p>GOAL 8: Minimize the impact of climate change and ocean acidification on biodiversity and increase its resilience through mitigation, adaptation, and disaster risk reduction actions, including through nature-based solution and/or ecosystem-based approaches, while minimizing negative and fostering positive impacts of climate action on biodiversity.</p>	<p>Climate Action Subprogramme</p> <p>i) Number of national, subnational and private-sector actors that adopt climate change mitigation and/or adaptation and disaster risk reduction strategies and policies with UNEP support</p> <p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p>
1.1.5: Pollution is reduced to levels that are not harmful to biodiversity, ecosystem functions and human health in a part of the most important sources affecting CBC priorities to be determined by consensus with countries.	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of priority pollutant sources that have reduced their pollution to levels that minimize the impact on biodiversity.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> At least 50% of priority pollution sources reduce their impact to a minimum</p>	<p>6.3.1 Proportion of domestic and industrial wastewater flows safely treated</p> <p>6.3.2 Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality</p> <p>14.1.1 (a) Index of coastal eutrophication; and (b) plastic debris density</p>	<p>GOAL 7: Reduce pollution risks and the negative impact of pollution from all sources, by 2030, to levels that are not harmful to biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services, considering cumulative effects, including: reducing excess nutrients lost to the environment by at least half including through more efficient nutrient cycling and use; reducing the overall risk from pesticides and highly hazardous chemicals by at least half including through integrated pest management, based on science, taking into account food security and livelihoods; and also preventing, reducing, and working towards eliminating plastic pollution.</p>	<p>Chemicals and Pollution Action Subprogramme</p> <p>ii) Number of Governments developing or implementing policies, strategies and mechanisms to prevent or reduce waste and ensure environmentally sound waste treatment or disposal, including in the context of disaster or conflict-related environmental emergencies, with UNEP support</p> <p>iv) Reduction in releases of pollutants to the environment achieved with UNEP support</p>
1.2 Territorial development of the key landscapes and seascapes of the CBC is planned with a spatial, holistic, and cooperative approach	<p><i>Indicator:</i> % of the surface of the CBC that has multisectoral and integrated territorial plans that consider biodiversity of regional importance</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> at least 80% of the key areas of the CBC with integrated and multisectoral plans</p>	<p>11.a.1 Number of countries that have national urban policies or regional development plans that (a) respond to population dynamics; (b) ensure balanced territorial development; and (c) increase local fiscal space</p> <p>13.2.1 Number of countries with nationally determined contributions, long-term strategies, national adaptation plans and adaptation communications, as reported to the secretariat of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change</p> <p>13.b.1 Number of least developed countries and small island developing States with nationally determined contributions, long-term strategies, national adaptation plans and adaptation communications, as reported to the secretariat of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change</p> <p>15.9.1 Progress towards national targets established in accordance with Aichi Biodiversity Target 2 of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020</p>	<p>GOAL 2</p> <p>GOAL 3</p> <p>GOAL 14 Ensure the full integration of biodiversity and its multiple values into policies, regulations, planning and development processes, poverty eradication strategies, strategic environmental assessments, environmental impact assessments and, as appropriate, national accounting, within and across all levels of government and across all sectors, in particular those with significant impacts on biodiversity, progressively aligning all relevant public and private activities, fiscal and financial flows with the goals and Goals of this framework.</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iii) Number of countries and national, regional and subnational authorities and entities that incorporate, with UNEP support, biodiversity and ecosystem-based approaches into development and sectoral plans, policies and processes for the sustainable management and/or restoration of terrestrial, freshwater and marine areas</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p>

Goal 1: The integrity and connectivity of all priority ecosystems is improved				
Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ¹	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
Milestones showing progress towards achieving the outcome of the plan	Dates when milestones are expected			
A study is carried out and a baseline of the number of existing plans is determined	Dec-2024			
Period analyzes of progress are carried out	Every two years			
40% plan coverage is reached	Dec-2027			
80% plan coverage is reached	Dec-2030			
Outputs for Outcome 1.2				
1.2.1 Coastal marine and Terrestrial Key areas for the CBC are under a multisectoral, participative and integrated land use planning scheme that considers biodiversity.	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of key areas of the CBC that have multisectoral and integrated territorial plans that consider biodiversity of regional importance.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target</i> at least 80% of CBC areas with integrated and multisectoral plans</p>	<p>11.a.1 Number of countries that have national urban policies or regional development plans that (a) respond to population dynamics; (b) ensure balanced territorial development; and (c) increase local fiscal space</p> <p>13.2.1 Number of countries with nationally determined contributions, long-term strategies, national adaptation plans and adaptation communications, as reported to the secretariat of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change</p> <p>13.b.1 Number of least developed countries and small island developing States with nationally determined contributions, long-term strategies, national adaptation plans and adaptation communications, as reported to the secretariat of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change</p> <p>15.9.1 Progress towards national targets established in accordance with Aichi Biodiversity Target 2 of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011-2020</p>	GOAL 14	<p>Nature action Subprogramme</p> <p>iii) Number of countries and national, regional and subnational authorities and entities that incorporate, with UNEP support, biodiversity and ecosystem-based approaches into development and sectoral plans, policies and processes for the sustainable management and/or restoration of terrestrial, freshwater and marine areas</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p>

GOAL 2: The contributions of terrestrial and marine ecosystem goods and services are valued and maintained or enhanced through sustainable use of resources, and support the development agenda to benefit all, particularly most vulnerable communities.

Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ²	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
2.1 Long-term sustainability of nature-based livelihoods and enterprises is ensured	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Increase in priority agricultural, fishing and forestry areas for the CBC that implement sustainable practices and livelihoods.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> At least 100% increase</p>	<p>2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status</p> <p>2.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture</p> <p>14.4.1 Proportion of fish stocks within biologically sustainable levels</p> <p>15.2.1 Progress towards sustainable forest management</p> <p>15.b.1 (a) Official development assistance on conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; and (b) revenue generated and finance mobilized from biodiversity-relevant economic instruments</p>	<p>GOAL 9: Ensure that the management and use of wild species are sustainable, thereby providing social, economic and environmental benefits for people, especially those in vulnerable situations and those most dependent on biodiversity, including through sustainable biodiversity-based activities, products and services that enhance biodiversity, and protecting and encouraging customary sustainable use by indigenous peoples and local communities.</p> <p>GOAL 10: Ensure that areas under agriculture, aquaculture, fisheries and forestry are managed sustainably, in particular through the sustainable use of biodiversity, including through a substantial increase of the application of biodiversity friendly practices, such as sustainable intensification, or ecological and other innovative approaches contributing to the resilience and long-term efficiency and productivity of these production systems and to food security, conserving and restoring biodiversity and maintaining nature's contributions to people, including ecosystem functions and services.</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p> <p>v) Positive shift in public opinion, attitudes and actions in support of biodiversity and ecosystem approaches</p> <p>vi) Positive shift in the private sector in support of biodiversity and ecosystem approaches</p>
Milestones showing progress towards achieving the outcome of the plan	Dates when milestones are expected			
The scientific and methodological basis is developed to measure progress towards this result, a baseline is established, and a specific action plan is formulated for the implementation of sustainable livelihoods and practices.	Dec-2024			
Sustainable development actions are implemented in at least half of the growth potential	Dec-2027			
Implementation of the plan is completed	Dec-2030			
Outputs for Outcome 2.1				
2.1.1 Incentives and tools that promote the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity are incorporated and sustainable practices and livelihoods are promoted and implemented in at least 50% of the priority agricultural, fishing and forestry areas for the CBC.	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Increase in the number of PAs and other prioritized areas that implement incentives and tools for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> By 2031, at least 50% of prioritized areas implement some type of incentive</p>	<p>14.5.1 Coverage of protected areas in relation to marine areas</p> <p>15.1.1 Forest area as a proportion of total land area</p> <p>15.1.2 Proportion of important sites for terrestrial and freshwater biodiversity that are covered by protected areas, by ecosystem type</p> <p>15.b.1 (a) Official development assistance on conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; and (b) revenue generated and finance mobilized from biodiversity-relevant economic instruments</p>	<p>GOAL 11</p> <p>GOAL 18: Identify by 2025, and eliminate, phase out or reform incentives, including subsidies, harmful for biodiversity, in a proportionate, just, fair, effective and equitable way, while substantially and progressively reducing them by at least 500 billion United States dollars per year by 2030, starting with the most harmful incentives, and scale up positive incentives for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity.</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p>

GOAL 2: The contributions of terrestrial and marine ecosystem goods and services are valued and maintained or enhanced through sustainable use of resources, and support the development agenda to benefit all, particularly most vulnerable communities.

Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ²	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> % of CBC priority agricultural, fisheries and forestry areas that implement sustainable livelihoods and practices.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> By 2031 at least 50% of CBC priority agriculture, fisheries and forestry areas implement sustainable livelihoods and practices.</p>	<p>2.3.2 Average income of small-scale food producers, by sex and indigenous status</p> <p>2.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture</p>	<p>GOAL 9.</p> <p>GOAL 10.</p> <p>GOAL 11.</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p> <p>v) Positive shift in public opinion, attitudes and actions in support of biodiversity and ecosystem approaches</p> <p>vi) Positive shift in the private sector in support of biodiversity and ecosystem approaches</p>
<p>2.1.2 Awareness and understanding of human-wildlife interactions, the social and environmental impacts of unsustainable use of natural resources, and the benefits of alternative livelihoods at local, national, and international regional scales are strengthened.</p>	<p><i>Indicator:</i> % of communities that improve their environmental awareness of biodiversity and its importance.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> By 2031 at least 50% of CBC priority communities have improved awareness and understanding of human-wildlife interactions, the social and environmental impacts of unsustainable use of natural resources, and the benefits of alternative livelihoods.</p>	<p>4.7.1 Extent to which (i) global citizenship education and (ii) education for sustainable development are mainstreamed in (a) national education policies; (b) curricula; (c) teacher education; and (d) student assessment</p> <p>12.8.1 Extent to which (i) global citizenship education and (ii) education for sustainable development are mainstreamed in (a) national education policies; (b) curricula; (c) teacher education; and (d) student assessment</p>	<p>GOAL 16: Ensure that people are encouraged and enabled to make sustainable consumption choices including by establishing supportive policy, legislative or regulatory frameworks, improving education and access to relevant and accurate information and alternatives, and by 2030, reduce the global footprint of consumption in an equitable manner, including through halving global food waste, significantly reducing overconsumption and substantially reducing waste generation, in order for all people to live well in harmony with Mother Earth</p> <p>GOAL 21: Ensure that the best available data, information and knowledge, are accessible to decision makers, practitioners and the public to guide effective and equitable governance, integrated and participatory management of biodiversity, and to strengthen communication, awareness-raising, education, monitoring, research and knowledge management and, also in this context, traditional knowledge, innovations, practices and technologies of indigenous peoples and local communities should only be accessed with their free, prior and informed consent², in accordance with national legislation.</p>	<p>Climate Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iv) Positive shift in public opinion, attitudes and actions in support of climate action as a result of UNEP action</p> <p>v) Positive shift among private sector actors in support of climate action as a result of UNEP engagement</p> <p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>v) Positive shift in public opinion, attitudes and actions in support of biodiversity and ecosystem approaches</p> <p>vi) Positive shift in the private sector in support of biodiversity and ecosystem approaches</p> <p>Finance and economic transformations</p> <p>iii) Number of consumer information tools and measures, educational approaches and advocacy and awareness-raising events and products that inform decision-making, choices and changes in behavior towards enhanced environmental sustainability, developed with UNEP support</p>

² Free, prior and informed consent refers to the tripartite terminology of "prior and informed consent" or "free, prior and informed consent" or "approval and involvement."

GOAL 2: The contributions of terrestrial and marine ecosystem goods and services are valued and maintained or enhanced through sustainable use of resources, and support the development agenda to benefit all, particularly most vulnerable communities.

Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ²	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
2.2 Contributions of terrestrial, coastal, and marine ecosystem goods and services are accounted for to support decision-making.	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Increase in the amount of PA and other priority areas that implement incentives and tools for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity incentives</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> At least 100% increase</p>	15.9.1 Progress towards national targets established in accordance with Aichi Biodiversity Target 2 of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011-2020	GOAL 11 GOAL 14	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iii) Number of countries and national, regional and subnational authorities and entities that incorporate, with UNEP support, biodiversity and ecosystem-based approaches into development and sectoral plans, policies and processes for the sustainable management and/or restoration of terrestrial, freshwater and marine areas</p> <p>iv) Increase in territory of land- and seascapes that is under improved ecosystem conservation and restoration</p>
Milestones showing progress towards achieving the outcome of the plan	Dates when milestones are expected			
The scientific and methodological basis for measuring progress towards this result is developed, a baseline is established, and a specific action plan is formulated for the implementation of actions that lead to the expected result	Dec-2025			
It is ensured that national contributions to the CBC are systematically accounted for and reported	Dec-2027			
It is ensured that nature's contributions to national and local economies in CBC priority areas have been assessed, accounted for, and considered in development decisions.	Dec-2030			
It ensures that productive activities and financial flows in the initiative consider the values of biodiversity.	Dec-2030			

GOAL 2: The contributions of terrestrial and marine ecosystem goods and services are valued and maintained or enhanced through sustainable use of resources, and support the development agenda to benefit all, particularly most vulnerable communities.

Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ²	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
Outputs for Outcome 2.2				
<p>2.2.1: National contributions to conservation in the CBC, and the value of ecosystem services are accounted for, and the alignment of financial instruments and flows with the values of biodiversity is measured.</p>	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of countries that account for their contribution to the CBC and report it.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 5</p> <p><i>Target:</i> All</p>	<p>15.9.1 Progress towards national targets established in accordance with Aichi Biodiversity Target 2 of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011-2020</p>	<p>GOAL 19: Substantially and progressively increase the level of financial resources from all sources, in an effective, timely and easily accessible manner, including domestic, international, public and private resources, in accordance with Article 20 of the Convention, to implement national biodiversity strategies and action plans, by 2030 mobilizing at least 200 billion United States dollars per year, including by:</p> <p>(a) Increasing total biodiversity related international financial resources from developed countries, including official development assistance, and from countries that voluntarily assume obligations of developed country Parties, to developing countries, in particular the least developed countries and small island developing States, as well as countries with economies in transition, to at least US\$ 20 billion per year by 2025, and to at least US\$ 30 billion per year by 2030;</p> <p>(b) Significantly increasing domestic resource mobilization, facilitated by the preparation and implementation of national biodiversity finance plans or similar instruments according to national needs, priorities and circumstances;</p> <p>(c) Leveraging private finance, promoting blended finance, implementing strategies for raising new and additional resources, and encouraging the private sector to invest in biodiversity, including through impact funds and other instruments;</p> <p>(d) Stimulating innovative schemes such as payment for ecosystem services, green bonds, biodiversity offsets and credits, benefit-sharing mechanisms, with environmental and social safeguards</p> <p>(e) Optimizing co-benefits and synergies of finance Goaling the biodiversity and climate crises,</p> <p>(f) Enhancing the role of collective actions, including by indigenous peoples and local communities, Mother Earth centric actions³ and non-market-based approaches including community based natural resource management and civil society cooperation and solidarity aimed at the conservation of biodiversity</p> <p>(g) Enhancing the effectiveness, efficiency and transparency of resource provision and use;</p>	<p>N/A</p>

³ Mother Earth Centric Actions: Ecocentric and rights-based approach enabling the implementation of actions towards harmonic and complementary relationships between peoples and nature, promoting the continuity of all living beings and their communities and ensuring the non-commodification of environmental functions of Mother Earth

GOAL 2: The contributions of terrestrial and marine ecosystem goods and services are valued and maintained or enhanced through sustainable use of resources, and support the development agenda to benefit all, particularly most vulnerable communities.

Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ²	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> % of the CBC demarcation that has evaluated the contribution of ecosystems to economies.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2024</p> <p><i>Target:</i> 100% of priority areas</p>	<p>15.9.1 Progress towards national targets established in accordance with Aichi Biodiversity Target 2 of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020</p>	<p>GOAL 19.</p>	
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of productive activities that internalize the values of biodiversity.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> TBD</p>	<p>.4.1 Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture</p> <p>15.9.1 Progress towards national targets established in accordance with Aichi Biodiversity Target 2 of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020</p>	<p>GOAL 10</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>iii) Number of countries and national, regional and subnational authorities and entities that incorporate, with UNEP support, biodiversity and ecosystem-based approaches into development and sectoral plans, policies and processes for the sustainable management and/or restoration of terrestrial, freshwater and marine areas</p>
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of countries that require environmental impact assessments to include biodiversity values.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> All countries of the initiative</p>	<p>15.9.1 Progress towards national targets established in accordance with Aichi Biodiversity Target 2 of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020</p>	<p>GOAL 14</p>	<p>Nature action Subprogramme</p> <p>iii) Number of countries and national, regional and subnational authorities and entities that incorporate, with UNEP support, biodiversity and ecosystem-based approaches into development and sectoral plans, policies and processes for the sustainable management and/or restoration of terrestrial, freshwater and marine areas</p>

GOAL 3: The gap between the necessary and available knowledge and resources is closed, and the conditions to achieve the 2050 Vision are ensured.

Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ²	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
3.1 The financial resources necessary to implement the CBC Strategic Plan are available and implemented.	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Amount of money secured in the CBC's endowment funds and generating interest for the initiative.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> \$27 million for the UNEP fund and 15 million for the CBF fund</p>	17.3.1 Additional financial resources mobilized for developing countries from multiple sources	GOAL 19	<p>Climate Action Subprogramme</p> <p>ii) Amounts provided and mobilized in \$ per year in relation to the continued existing collective mobilization goal of the \$100 billion commitment through to 2025 with UNEP support</p>
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Amount of money secured in projects for actions in the field that respond to the strategic plan.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> \$30 million (20 million external financing and 10 million national contributions).</p>	17.3.1 Additional financial resources mobilized for developing countries from multiple sources	GOAL 19	<p>Climate Action Subprogramme</p> <p>ii) Amounts provided and mobilized in \$ per year in relation to the continued existing collective mobilization goal of the \$100 billion commitment through to 2025 with UNEP support</p>
Milestones showing progress towards achieving the outcome of the plan	Dates when milestones are expected			
A financing plan is established	Dec-2022			
Projects are started for an amount of at least USD 2.5 million	Jan-2023			
Resources are raised to start both endowment funds and the financing plan is updated	Dec-2023			
Countries will secure national funds that contribute to the strategic plan	Dec-2024			
Other cooperation projects are sought to complete the goal	Dec-2024			
Additional resources are raised to complete both endowment funds	Dec-2027			
Outputs for Outcome 3.1				
3.1.1 It is ensured that the financial resources of regional scope necessary to achieve the objectives and goals of the initiative are gradually increased.	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Amount of money raised for endowment funds</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> US \$ 42 M.</p>	17.3.1 Additional financial resources mobilized for developing countries from multiple sources	GOAL 19	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>ii) Number of financial, public- and private-sector entities whose financial decisions and risk management frameworks take biodiversity and ecosystem services into consideration, and the increase in financial flows towards ecosystem management as a result of UNEP support</p>

GOAL 3: The gap between the necessary and available knowledge and resources is closed, and the conditions to achieve the 2050 Vision are ensured.

Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ²	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Amount of sinking funds committed for projects</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> US \$ 30 M raised until 2030</p>			
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Average amount implemented per year until 2030</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0.8 M/year on average</p> <p><i>Target:</i> US \$ 3.3 M/year as average of the period</p>	<p>17.3.1 Additional financial resources mobilized for developing countries from multiple sources</p>	<p>GOAL 19</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>ii) Number of financial, public- and private-sector entities whose financial decisions and risk management frameworks take biodiversity and ecosystem services into consideration, and the increase in financial flows towards ecosystem management as a result of UNEP support</p>
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Insured amount for the period 2031-2040</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> At least US\$30 M (1 MM/year return on endowment funds + 1 M/year for projects+1 M/year for national contributions)</p>	<p>17.3.1 Additional financial resources mobilized for developing countries from multiple sources</p>	<p>GOAL 19</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>ii) Number of financial, public- and private-sector entities whose financial decisions and risk management frameworks take biodiversity and ecosystem services into consideration, and the increase in financial flows towards ecosystem management as a result of UNEP support</p>
<p>3.2 Strengthened capacity of the CBC as a governance mechanism and South-South cooperation platform for capacity building, knowledge generation, and facilitating access to relevant information for decision-making for the benefit of national and local governments, and communities, and to implement the CBC Strategic Action Plan in both the marine and terrestrial realm.</p>	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of decisions made by Ministerial Committees and percentage of implementation.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> One meeting every 1.5 years. 80% average implementation (to be adjusted in Dec-2022)</p> <p><i>Target:</i> At least 7 ministerial meetings with decisions, of which 90% are implemented by Dec-2030</p>	<p>16.8.1 Proportion of members and voting rights of developing countries in international organizations</p>	<p>GOAL 21</p> <p>GOAL 22 Ensure the full, equitable, inclusive, effective and gender-responsive representation and participation in decision-making, and access to justice and information related to biodiversity by indigenous peoples and local communities, respecting their cultures and their rights over lands, territories, resources, and traditional knowledge, as well as by women and girls, children and youth, and persons with disabilities and ensure the full protection of environmental human rights defenders.</p>	<p>Science-Policy Subprogramme</p> <p>ii) Number of relevant global, regional and national forums, institutions and Governments using data, statistics, scientific assessments and early warning and foresight systems provided by UNEP for catalyzing policymaking and action</p> <p>Environmental Governance Subprogramme</p> <p>iii) Number of plans, approaches, strategies, policies, action plans or budgeting processes of entities at the national, regional and global levels that include environmental goals as a result of UNEP support</p>

GOAL 3: The gap between the necessary and available knowledge and resources is closed, and the conditions to achieve the 2050 Vision are ensured.

Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ²	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Increase in the annual average of tasks directly carried out by the Secretariat</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> 50% of the average increase</p>	N/A	N/A	N/A
Milestones showing progress towards achieving the outcome of the plan	Dates when milestones are expected			
The Executive Secretariat is strengthened with young staff, female participation and completing functions (Communication and ICT)	Dec-2023			
IACS is completed, updated, and developed	Dec-2025			
Monitoring of the initiative and of biodiversity is strengthened	Dec-2026			
Legal and policy gaps are filled to:	Dec-2028			
Outputs for Outcome 3.2				
3.2.1. The best available and relevant knowledge, including traditional knowledge, guides decision-making for the effective management of biological diversity in the CBC and beyond.	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Percentage of requests for new functions and tools satisfied in the IKMS</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> 80% of demands met at the end of the plan</p>	<p>17.6.1 Number of science and/or technology cooperation agreements and programmes between countries, by type of cooperation</p> <p>17.7.1 Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies</p>	<p>GOAL 20</p> <p>GOAL 21</p>	<p>Science-policy Subprogramme</p> <p>i) Number of countries and national, regional and subnational authorities that, as a result of UNEP support, have strengthened capacity to develop sound environmental data, statistics, scientific assessments and early warning systems</p> <p>Finance and Economic Transformations Subprogramme</p> <p>iii) Number of consumer information tools and measures, educational approaches and advocacy and awareness-raising events and products that inform decision-making, choices and changes in behavior towards enhanced environmental sustainability, developed with UNEP support</p> <p>Digital Transformations subprogramme</p> <p>ii) Number of business alliances, partnerships and networks leveraging environmental data and digital transformation approaches to incentivize environmental sustainability and a circular economy within financial markets</p>

GOAL 3: The gap between the necessary and available knowledge and resources is closed, and the conditions to achieve the 2050 Vision are ensured.

Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ²	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Increase in the number of new documents, databases, and layers of geographic information available.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in 2023</p> <p><i>Target:</i> 25% increase at the end of the plan</p>	<p>17.7.1 Total amount of funding for developing countries to promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies</p>	<p>GOAL 20</p> <p>GOAL 21</p>	<p>Science-policy Subprogramme</p> <p>i) Number of countries and national, regional and subnational authorities that, as a result of UNEP support, have strengthened capacity to develop sound environmental data, statistics, scientific assessments and early warning systems</p> <p>Finance and Economic Transformations Subprogramme</p> <p>iii) Number of consumer information tools and measures, educational approaches and advocacy and awareness-raising events and products that inform decision-making, choices and changes in behavior towards enhanced environmental sustainability, developed with UNEP support</p>
<p>3.2.2 It is ensured that legislation, policies, regulations, territorial plans, development processes and poverty reduction strategies explicitly consider and favor the conservation and restoration of biological diversity values, in all relevant sectors in the spatial scope of the CBC.</p>	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of key policies, plans, regulations and/or legal instruments that have been modified to ensure that they explicitly consider and favor the conservation and restoration of biological diversity values.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> At least one key instrument modified per country.</p>	<p>14.5.1 Coverage of protected areas in relation to marine areas</p> <p>15.8.1 Proportion of countries adopting relevant national legislation and adequately resourcing the prevention or control of invasive alien species</p> <p>15.9.1 Progress towards national targets established in accordance with Aichi Biodiversity Target 2 of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011-2020</p>	<p>GOAL 14</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>i) Number of national or subnational entities that, with UNEP support, adopt integrated approaches to address environmental and social issues and/or tools for valuing, monitoring and sustainably managing biodiversity</p> <p>iii) Number of countries and national, regional and subnational authorities and entities that incorporate, with UNEP support, biodiversity and ecosystem-based approaches into development and sectoral plans, policies and processes for the sustainable management and/or restoration of terrestrial, freshwater and marine areas</p> <p>v) Positive shift in public opinion, attitudes and actions in support of biodiversity and ecosystem approaches</p> <p>vi) Positive shift in the private sector in support of biodiversity and ecosystem approaches</p> <p>Environmental Governance Subprogramme</p> <p>iii) Number of plans, approaches, strategies, policies, action plans or budgeting processes of entities at the national, regional and global levels that include environmental goals as a result of UNEP support</p>
<p>3.2.3 Capacities of key actors for productive and ecological restoration of terrestrial and marine ecosystems are strengthened; EbA, planning and integrated management of the sustainable use of natural resources; and to assess the socio-ecological impacts of restoration and conservation initiatives.</p>	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of key actors with strengthened capacities</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> At least 5 key actors (organizations) per country</p>	<p>4.7.1 Extent to which (i) global citizenship education and (ii) education for sustainable development are mainstreamed in (a) national education policies; (b) curricula; (c) teacher education; and (d) student assessment</p> <p>12.8.1 Extent to which (i) global citizenship education and (ii) education for sustainable development are mainstreamed in (a) national education policies; (b) curricula; (c) teacher education; and (d) student assessment</p>	<p>GOAL 16</p> <p>GOAL 20</p>	<p>Nature Action Subprogramme</p> <p>v) Positive shift in public opinion, attitudes and actions in support of biodiversity and ecosystem approaches</p> <p>vi) Positive shift in the private sector in support of biodiversity and ecosystem approaches</p>

GOAL 3: The gap between the necessary and available knowledge and resources is closed, and the conditions to achieve the 2050 Vision are ensured.

Outcome	Indicators	SDG Indicators and Achievements	Global Biodiversity Framework Goals ²	Indicators and expected accomplishments for the relevant UNEP Subprogramme
3.2.4 The capacity of the Executive Secretariat of the CBC and of the initiative in general is strengthened and renewed	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Number of young staff in the Secretariat with at least 33% female participation.</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> 0</p> <p><i>Target:</i> 3, at least one woman</p>	<p>5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex</p> <p>5.5.1 Proportion of seats held by women in (a) national parliaments and (b) local governments</p> <p>5.5.2 Proportion of Women in managerial positions</p>	<p>GOAL 22</p> <p>GOAL 23 Ensure gender equality in the implementation of the framework through a gender-responsive approach where all women and girls have equal opportunity and capacity to contribute to the three objectives of the Convention, including by recognizing their equal rights and access to land and natural resources and their full, equitable, meaningful and informed participation and leadership at all levels of action, engagement, policy and decision-making related to biodiversity.”</p>	N/A
	<p><i>Indicator:</i> Annual average of key tasks directly performed by Secretariat staff</p> <p><i>Baseline:</i> To be determined in Dec-2022</p> <p><i>Target:</i> At least equal to the average number of tasks per person per year</p>	N/A	N/A	N/A

